

Co-UDlabs

Building Collaborative Urban Drainage
research Labs communities

D1.3 Strategy for RI Sustainability and Community Development

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Background: about the Co-UDlabs Project

Co-UDlabs is an EU-funded project aiming to integrate research and innovation activities in the field of Urban Drainage Systems (UDS) to address pressing public health, flood risks and environmental challenges.

Bringing together 17 unique research facilities, Co-UDlabs offers training and free access to a wide range of high-level scientific instruments, smart monitoring technologies and digital water analysis tools for advancing knowledge and innovation in Urban drainage systems.

Co-UDlabs aims to create an urban drainage large-scale facilities network to provide opportunities for monitoring water quality, UDS performance and smart and open data approaches.

The main objective of the project is to provide a transnational multidisciplinary collaborative research infrastructure that will allow stakeholders, academic researchers, and innovators in the urban drainage water sector to come together, share ideas, co-produce project concepts and then benefit from access to top-class research infrastructures to develop, improve and demonstrate those concepts, thereby building a collaborative European Urban Drainage innovation community.

The initiative will facilitate the uptake of innovation in traditional buried pipe systems and newer green-blue infrastructure, with a focus on increasing the understanding of asset deterioration and improving system resilience.

List of acronyms

Acronym / Abbreviation	Meaning / Full text
AEAS	Asociación Española de Abastecimientos de Agua y Saneamiento
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AIR	Assessment of Inspection Tools for Rising
BDEW	Bundesverband der Energie- und Wasserwirtschaft e. V.
CA	Consortium Agreement
CCS	Community-based Competence Centres
CENTA	Centro Experimental de Nuevas Tecnologías del Agua
CETAQUA	Centro Tecnológico del Agua
CIWEM	Chartered Institution of Water and Environmental Management
CSO	Combined sewer overflow
DANVA	Danish Water and Wastewater Association
DVGW	Deutscher Verein des Gas- und Wasserfaches e.V.
GA	Grant Agreement
EC	European Commission
EJWS	European Junior Scientists Workshop
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ERA	European Research Area
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
EU	European Union
EWA	European Water Association
EAWAG	Eidgenössische Anstalt für Wasserversorgung, Abwasserreinigung und Gewässerschutz
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
HPC	High-Performance Computing
IAHR	International Association for Hydro-Environment Engineering and Research
ICUD	International Conference on Urban Drainage
IKT	Institute for Underground Infrastructure
INFRAIA	Integrating Activities for Advanced Communities

Acronym / Abbreviation	Meaning / Full text
IWA	International Water Association
JCUD	Joint Committee on Urban Drainage
JRA	Joint Research Activity
JRC	Joint Research Centre
KNW	Royal Dutch Water Network
KWB	Kompetenzzentrum Wasser Berlin
MSCA	Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions
Nbs	Nature-based Solutions
OSCARS	Open Science Cluster for Advancing Research
REA	Research Executive Agency
RI	Research Infrastructure
SfM	Structure-from-Motion
STOWA	Stichting Toegepast Onderzoek Waterbeheer
SuDS	Sustainable urban Drainage Systems
SWV	Schweizerische Wasserwirtschaftsverband
TA	Transnational Access
UD	Urban Drainage
UDC	Universidade da Coruña
UDM	Urban Drainage Modelling Conference
UDMT	Urban Drainage Metrology Toolbox
UDS	Urban Drainage System
UKWIR	UK Water Industry Research
USFD	University of Sheffield
VSA	Verband Schweizer Abwasser- und Gewässerschutzfachleute
WOLLS	Water Oriented Living Labs

Executive summary

This document is a deliverable of the Co-UDlabs project, funded under the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101008626.

The aim of this document is to: long-term development and integration of research infrastructure across Europe

The deliverable presents the strategic vision of Co-UDlabs for ensuring the long-term sustainability and development of research infrastructures (RIs) in the field of Urban Drainage Systems (UDS) across Europe. Co-UDlabs has successfully brought together 17 high-level RIs and a diverse community of researchers, practitioners, and stakeholders. Through extensive networking, training, Transnational Access (TA), and dissemination activities, the project has laid the groundwork for a collaborative European ecosystem of UDS research and innovation.

The strategy outlined in this report builds on lessons learned throughout the project and addresses key priorities, including increasing visibility and accessibility of RIs, fostering cross-disciplinary collaboration, enhancing knowledge exchange, and identifying future funding pathways. Co-UDlabs also led the formation of the UDRAIN Working Group within the JCUD, which seeks to consolidate global efforts in UDS RIs through a dedicated atlas and shared standards and new training and collaborative funding opportunities.

By engaging with EU and national communities, building partnerships with industry and utilities, and exploring new funding mechanisms—such as ESFRI, ERIC, and Open Science initiatives—Co-UDlabs charts a path toward a resilient, inclusive, and innovation-driven network of urban drainage RIs that responds to real-world challenges in climate resilience, public health, and environmental protection.

1. Introduction

This task was focused on the long-term development and integration of research infrastructure across Europe to meet the long-term research and dissemination needs of the EU water sector as regards UDS. A strategy has been developed for the long-term consolidation of a European Urban Drainage RIs community, based on the Co-UDlabs experience. To develop the strategy, the different links with existing communities, EU and national projects and organizations coordinating relevant RIs to Co-UDlabs were analyzed to exchange know-how and good practices of operation. Relevant RIs of the consortium or external partners were also reviewed and contacted to assess the possibilities of expanding the network. Outcomes from Tasks 1.1 and 1.2, related to the definition of a wide range of users' needs, and our experience in the adoption of knowledge and technologies supported by different TA activities performed in the project, were also considered in the development of a Co-UDlabs strategy.

The draft strategy for the long-term development of common RIs at EU level to maximize impacts on research and policy implementation, as well as value creation have been reviewed by the International Advisory Board and external experts. The deliverable lists the actions required (by the Co-UDlabs partners and others) to sustain and build on the Co-UDlabs community for the common benefit of the EU water sector

2. Current Landscape of Research Infrastructures in Urban Drainage

2.1. Overview of Existing RIs and Their Role in UDS Research

Research Infrastructures (RIs) are key drivers in the transition towards smart and sustainable urban drainage systems (UDS). They provide the necessary platforms to develop, test, and validate new technologies, methods and tools while enhancing the understanding of existing structures. This contributes to informed, science-based decision-making, particularly in assessing the value and performance of sustainable options. One of the major advantages of RIs is their ability to collect evidence on a pilot scale under controlled or representative conditions, which is often difficult or impractical to achieve in real-world conditions due to safety concerns and unpredictable variables. By bridging the gap between research and field applications, RIs offer a controlled, flexible environment for experimentation, allowing researchers and industry actors to develop models and test innovative solutions before deploying them in real UDS. Water utilities are traditionally cautious innovation adopters that often require near-full scale testing of new solutions prior to widespread adoption. This adaptability ensures that RIs remain relevant as technologies evolve and best practices improve.

Beyond experimentation, RIs play a fundamental role in knowledge transfer. By producing credible data and validated methodologies, they build confidence among end users such as utilities, regulators, and practitioners, regarding the feasibility and reliability of new technologies. Across Europe, different countries have developed networks and structures to support water-related research and innovation. Within the countries participating in Co-UDlabs, these structures often share similar frameworks, which could be further strengthened by fostering connections between national and EU-level initiatives. For example: Denmark has the highest proportion of facilities focused on collaboration, while France demonstrates strong engagement with regulatory bodies, ensuring compliance and effective management practices. The Netherlands places particularly emphasis on knowledge brokerage, leveraging its expertise in water management. The United Kingdom stands out for its comprehensive approach of thematic aspects covered per structure — indicating a tendency towards overlap and integration; Switzerland follows closely, suggesting a similarly holistic approach. In contrast, Germany exhibits more specialized

and clearly defined roles within its water sector structures, potentially leading to greater operational efficiency. Strengthening internal (national-level) and external (EU-level) connections within these frameworks would enhance knowledge transfer, ensuring that RIs remain central hubs for innovation, collaboration, and community-building in urban drainage (Brelot et al., 2024).

Despite the structural differences across countries, a common vision unites RI users and owners: advancing sustainable, science-based urban drainage solutions and driving the transition toward more resilient, efficient water systems. Recognizing this, the UDRAIN Working Group was established as a pioneering initiative under the IWA-IAHR Joint Committee on Urban Drainage (JCUD). Its primary objective is to develop the first global network of large RIs dedicated to UDS, where technologies can be tested under controlled and/or real-world conditions. However, many of these RIs have traditionally been operated in isolation, with limited visibility and fragmented efforts, hindering the effective knowledge transfer and slowing the adoption of innovative drainage solutions by practitioners and water utilities at wide European scale.

2.2. Links with Existing Communities at EU and National level.

To develop its long-term strategy, Co-UDlabs analyzed its links with existing communities, as well as EU and national projects and organizations that coordinate relevant RIs. This analysis aimed to facilitate the exchange of know-how and good operational practices. Co-UDlabs recognizes the importance of fostering strong connections with water sector organizations to enhance knowledge exchange, collaboration, and the practical applications of research. By engaging with a diverse range of stakeholders, the project aimed to create a dynamic network where ideas can be shared, and project concepts co-developed. This commitment extends beyond its immediate partners, as Co-UDlabs actively collaborates with European organizations, ensuring that its research infrastructure aligns with sector needs and contributes to broader water management goals.

Engagement with EU Water Sector Organizations: At the EU level, Co-UDlabs interacts with key water operators and professional associations networks such as Water Europe and the European Water Association (EWA). Water Europe serves as a platform for connecting stakeholders across academia, utilities, and industry, supporting the transition toward water-smart societies. Co-UDlabs aims to strengthen its engagement with Water Europe to maximize its outreach and impact, benefiting from the opportunity that INSA Lyon researchers are members of Water Europe working groups. Similarly, EWA promotes sustainable water management and knowledge transfer across European countries. Co-UDlabs partners, including USFD and UDC, are now members of EWA's newly formed research group, facilitating collaboration and influencing European policy. Further reinforcing its links within the sector, Co-UDlabs collaborates with EurEau, an organization representing drinking water and wastewater service operators across Europe. EurEau plays a critical role in advocating policy advancements and innovative water management practices, working closely with the Joint Research Centre (JRC) to ensure research findings translate into practical solutions (Brelot et al., 2024).

The project also engages with the Water4All Partnership, a trans-continental initiative focused on water security, which has invited Co-UDlabs to present its research infrastructures and findings at key events. Furthermore, the whole Research Infrastructures of Co-UDlabs were included in the mapping of water related RIs¹ conducted by Water4all (Figure 1). These interactions enable Co-UDlabs to align its efforts with broader European initiatives and contribute to interconnected research infrastructures.

¹ [Mapping water related research infrastructure | European Partnership Water4All](#)

Building Collaborative Urban Drainage research lab communities 🇪🇺

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RI Acronym : Co-UDlabs

Institution/Coordinating Institution : Universidade da Coruña

Other partners : Universidade da Coruña (Spain) - University of Sheffield (UK) - Deltares (The Netherlands) - EAWAG (Switzerland) - IKT (Germany) - INSA-Lyon (France) - Aalborg University (Denmark) - GRAIE (France) - Euronovia (France)

Country : Spain

Current Status : Active

Location : CITEEC, Campus de Elviña s/n, A Coruña (Spain)

RI Type : Distributed RI (Central Hub and interlinked National Nodes RI)

Level of Access : Transnational

Cost of Access : Free

Keywords : Urban Drainage - Water Pollution - Flooding - Assets Deterioration - Suds

Water4All Keywords : Emerging contaminants - Water Infrastructures - Climate changes - Water technologies - Resilience and sustainability

Domains and thematic area : Sustainable Water Management

Services provided : Access monitoring sites - Numerical modeling - Access data and metadata - Training services

Equipment : Hydraulic laboratory - Observation networks and tools - Numerical modelling - Physical modelling

RIS LIST RIS MAP

MORE INFOS

Website :

Contact Name : Jose Anta Alvarez

Co-UDLABS (Building Collaborative Urban Drainage research lab communities) is a Horizon 2020 project funded under the Research Infrastructures programme (INFRAIA-02-2020 - Integrating Activities for Starting Communities). Bringing together 9 partners offering access to 17 unique research facilities, Co-UDlabs offers training and free access to a wide range of high-level scientific instruments, smart monitoring technologies and digital water analysis tools for advancing knowledge and innovation in Urban drainage systems.

Figure 1 Co-UDlabs information from Water4all partnership catalogue of water related Research Infrastructures¹.

On the international stage, Co-UDlabs maintains strong ties with the International Water Association (IWA) and the International Association for Hydro-Environment Engineering and Research (IAHR) through the Joint Committee on Urban Drainage - JCUD (<https://jicud.org/>). These connections foster collaboration with the global water community and support Co-UDlabs' mission to advance urban drainage research and practice. The initiative has taken part in around six major international events, some oriented towards professional and industry stakeholders (e.g., IWA World Water Congress and Novatech), and others focused on research audiences (e.g., SPN and ICUD) (Anta, Naves, Ciambra, Tait, et al., 2024).

Beyond these sector-specific organizations, Co-UDlabs also acknowledges the relevance of broader EU programs such as Interreg Europe and COST, which facilitate cooperation and knowledge transfer across scientific and regional initiatives. While not exclusively focused on water, these programs offer valuable opportunities for the urban drainage sector to engage in interdisciplinary research and policy development. Through these diverse collaborations, Co-UDlabs strengthens its role as a key actor in the water sector, ensuring that its research infrastructure remains relevant, accessible, and impactful (Brelot et al., 2024).

Links with Water Sector National Structures: Co-UDlabs recognizes the importance of national structures in shaping urban drainage research, policy, and practice across partner countries. In Denmark, the Danish Water and Wastewater Association (DANVA) provides a platform for collaboration between researchers and practitioners, while the Water Pollution Committee of The Society of Danish Engineers has been instrumental in advancing wastewater and urban drainage technology. France benefits from the active engagement of GRAIE, which connects research with practice through initiatives like OTHU and the Novatech conferences. Additionally, ASTEE and SHF, as French governing members of resp. IWA and IAHR, collaborate on urban hydrology, while OIEau offers training and supports national water management strategies under the guidance of the Ministry of Ecological Transition (Brelot et al., 2024; Tondera et al., 2022).

In Germany, KWB (Kompetenzzentrum Wasser Berlin) fosters applied water research in partnership with utilities, while BDEW (Bundesverband der Energie- und Wasserwirtschaft e. V.) represents water service providers and promotes sustainable water management. DVGW (Deutscher Verein des Gas- und Wasserfaches e.V.) plays a critical

role in setting technical standards and encouraging research in the sector. Spain's Asociación Española de Abastecimientos de Agua y Saneamiento (AEAS) has published technical guidelines to support urban drainage development, and organizations such as Fundación CENTA (Centro Experimental de Nuevas Tecnologías del Agua) and CETAQUA (Centro Tecnológico del Agua) work closely with municipalities and utilities to drive innovation in urban water management. Switzerland's water sector is supported by Zweckverbände (wastewater associations), while EAWAG, leads research efforts. VSA (Verband Schweizer Abwasser- und Gewässerschutzfachleute) has pioneered a data model for digital urban drainage data processing, and SWV (Schweizerische Wasserwirtschaftsverband) serves as a key association for water professionals (Brelot et al., 2024; Tondera et al., 2022).

The Netherlands has established a strong knowledge-sharing framework through KNW (Royal Dutch Water Network), which fosters collaboration among researchers, utilities, and policymakers. STOWA (Stichting Toegepast Onderzoek Waterbeheer) leads applied research in water management, and Stichting RIONED supports municipal urban drainage initiatives. In the United Kingdom, Water UK represents water and wastewater service providers, while UKWIR (UK Water Industry Research) plays a central role in coordinating and funding research across the country's utilities. CIWEM (Chartered Institution of Water and Environmental Management) promotes sustainable water management and acts as a hub for knowledge exchange, while the Environment Agency plays a crucial role in shaping urban drainage policies and implementation strategies (Brelot et al., 2024; Tondera et al., 2022).

By engaging with these national-level organizations, Co-UDlabs strengthens its connections with existing communities and ensures alignment with country-specific roadmaps for sustainable urban drainage. This approach enhances collaboration, supports policy development, and facilitates the exchange of best practices, ensuring that research efforts translate into tangible improvements in urban water management across Europe.

2.3. Community Development through Co-UDlabs

In addition to mapping the situation of the sector and establishing links with several existing communities and organizations, the activities of Co-UDlabs have allowed to significantly expand this network and promote the creation of a community of urban drainage research infrastructures.

Collaboration through Transnational Access (TA): The TA program was designed to create multi-sectoral teams involving academia, operators, industry, and policymakers, effectively bridging the gap between research and practical application. By enabling access to state-of-the-art research infrastructures, the program strengthens connections within existing scientific and professional communities while also expanding engagement with new stakeholders. The success of the TA program is evident in its diverse user groups, which include 227 user-group members from 26 countries (11 non-EU). Notably, 23.8% of participants were women, 29.5% were from non-EU countries, and 33% came from outside academia (Anta, Naves, Ciambra, & Puertas, 2024). This diversity strengthens existing research networks while forging new collaborations, allowing for the exchange of knowledge, best practices, and data across borders. The research infrastructures available through Co-UDlabs serve as hubs where practitioners bring real-world insights to research initiatives, ensuring that project development remains aligned with industry and operators needs and challenges.

Beyond facilitating access to research facilities, the TA program reinforces long-term professional relationships. By providing structured opportunities for interdisciplinary collaboration, the program supports the co-production of research concepts and strengthens the integration of complementary expertise. Closer interactions between academic researchers and industry professionals encourage cross-disciplinary exchange, leading to multi-sectoral

problem-solving and innovative thinking. Moreover, the program enhances synergies among research infrastructures, fostering a more cohesive and interconnected urban drainage research community in Europe.

Through these efforts, Co-UDlabs positions its research infrastructures as focal points for collaboration, reinforcing their role as essential nodes within the broader European research community. By uniting professionals across environmental research and hydraulics, the TA program contributes to a dynamic and inclusive research ecosystem that continues to thrive through sustained partnerships and shared expertise.

UDRAIN Working Group: Co-UDlabs established the UDRAIN working group of the JCUD. This initiative aims to coordinate RIs globally for better information sharing across Europe and to present a coordinated message to policymakers. UDRAIN seeks to establish a worldwide network of large RIs of UDS to foster cooperation, technical collaboration, and joint initiatives.

UDRAIN’s mission is to bridge this gap by providing a collaborative platform to map, connect, and strengthen the world’s large-scale urban drainage RIs, transforming them into engines for innovation, education, and global cooperation. Officially launched at the 16th International Conference on Urban Drainage (ICUD) in Delft, Netherlands, on June 11, 2024, UDRAIN quickly gained momentum, with 63 institutions across 30 countries expressing interest within just a few months (Figure 2). Notably, the majority of interested institutions come from academic backgrounds, with 83.1% of respondents affiliated with research centre or university (Figure 3). Their research spans a diverse range of topics and thematic areas such as sustainable urban drainage systems (SuDS), urban flooding, and run-off pollution comprising approximately 53% of all responses.

Figure 2 Map of countries of work of survey respondents (colour intensity denotes frequency of responses).

Figure 3 Types of entity/institutions and Thematic areas of survey respondents.

By November 2024, UDRAIN had established its core leadership group, ensuring an organized and efficient framework for advancing its objectives. These include the creation of a global inventory (Atlas) of large-scale urban drainage RIs to enhance visibility, access, and collaboration. UDRAIN also aims to promote technical cooperation and knowledge sharing among RI managers, researchers, practitioners, SMEs, and regulators. Additionally, it seeks to facilitate transnational access, building on the successful model of the Co-UDlabs project, while standardizing data collection, research protocols, and training activities. Through these efforts, UDRAIN fosters mutual learning and innovation, ensuring that infrastructure research addresses real-world needs and societal challenges in urban drainage. Moving forward, UDRAIN’s immediate priorities include publishing the first edition of its Atlas of RIs (Annex 1), with participation open through an online survey. It also aims to expand its membership to include private sector entities, local authorities, and utility practitioners. Planned activities include organizing training sessions, knowledge-sharing events, and dissemination campaigns. To further engage with the research community, UDRAIN will participate in major conferences, including a Co-UDlabs-hosted workshop at the upcoming Urban Drainage Modelling Conference (UDM) 2025 on September 15th in Innsbruck, Austria. These efforts will contribute to establishing a strong, sustainable, and inclusive network of urban drainage RIs, ultimately shaping the future of water-smart, resilient cities.

3. Lessons Learned from Co-UDlabs Experience

Throughout its lifetime, the project has engaged a wide and diverse range of users, from early-career researchers to industry professionals, utilities, municipalities, and non-academic actors. This diversity has been crucial in identifying both persistent challenges and emerging needs within the field.

Figure 4 Summary of main themes covered in lessons learned from Co-UDlabs experience.

This section presents the key lessons learned from the project’s operational experience, with a view to informing the design and execution of future RI initiatives. It synthesizes reflections drawn from multiple components of the project, including the TA program, networking and training activities, stakeholder feedback, and the strategic analysis of barriers and enablers for knowledge adoption (Figure 4).

3.1. Key Insights on Users' Needs from the developed roadmaps in networking activities

A clear understanding of stakeholder needs is essential to guide the development of SuDS and ensure the relevance of RI. As outlined in the deliverable D1.1 (Tondera et al., 2022), and D1.2 (Brelot et al., 2024) these needs were identified through a review of national policy documents, contributions from Co-UDlabs researchers, and feedback from current and potential RI users across the EU and associated countries. This assessment provides valuable insights into the diverse expectations surrounding sustainable and smart UDS, helping to align future research, infrastructure planning, and stakeholder engagement with practical demands. The following summary highlights the key user needs identified from these different perspectives.

Scientific knowledge and research: Potential users of research infrastructures have expressed the need for greater scientific knowledge in the field of real-time stormwater filtration, understanding the long-term performance of nature-based solutions (NbS), and developing integrated approaches to stormwater management from economic, scientific, and social perspectives. Research on overflow discharges, pollution accumulation on urban surfaces, and the impact of wet weather conditions on receiving water bodies remains crucial for effective environmental management.

Users emphasize the importance of improved data acquisition and processing, particularly through AI-driven models and big data analytics, to optimize asset management and predict system failures. There is also a clear demand for enhanced monitoring of pollutants and better understanding of sewer processes, including infiltration, exfiltration, and corrosion, which are essential for securing the long-term sustainability of urban drainage systems.

Additionally, advancing knowledge on the life cycle of urban drainage systems, including deterioration modeling and rehabilitation cost assessment, will support the development of sustainable infrastructure (Anta, Naves, Ciambra, Tait, et al., 2024). Joint research efforts must continue to focus on improving the resilience and efficiency of stormwater management practices, ensuring that scientific advancements translate into practical, real-world applications. Through its collaborative approach, Co-UDlabs contributes to meeting these knowledge gaps, fostering interdisciplinary research, and supporting a more resilient and sustainable urban water management framework.

Integration and RI development: Effective urban drainage management in the face of climate change requires a paradigm shift toward more integrated and adaptive infrastructure solutions. Integrating water supply and groundwater with UDS is necessary to i) understand infiltration or exfiltration problems, and ii) develop a synoptic approach on water resources, uses and transfers at city scale and beyond in a context a rapidly evolving climate change. There is a need to build or improve sewer systems today to prepare them to handle the climatic events of tomorrow, anticipating future changes. Knowledge about future rainfall and hazards is essential for planning and adapting urban drainage infrastructure.

In this context, the development and modernization of RI play a key role. Future-ready RI assets must be flexible, multifunctional, and designed to accommodate evolving research needs and methodologies. These infrastructures not only support innovation in inspection, maintenance, and repair strategies, but also foster cross-sector collaboration and knowledge transfer. Enhancing national awareness and accessibility of RI, while ensuring quality and standardization of metrology methods, can bridge gaps between research and practice. Moreover, RIs must be aligned with circular economy principles, supporting sustainable infrastructure solutions and ensuring effective dissemination of research outcomes to practitioners and stakeholders alike.

A shift toward integrated UDS is also marked by the convergence of traditional grey infrastructure with NbS, forming hybrid green-grey systems that deliver both technical performance and ecosystem services. Integrated catchment management and planning — across urban planning, road infrastructure, green space, and water authorities — are crucial to address water challenges in a coherent and coordinated manner. Emphasizing the connection between drainage systems, wastewater treatment plants, and receiving waters is vital to align with holistic frameworks like the EU Water Framework Directive or the recast of Urban Wastewater Directive, and to promote synergistic regulation and management.

Hybrid Green and Grey Infrastructure strategy promoted by Water Europe (Water Europe, 2022) allows to create (climate) resilient water systems that reliably control peak flows, deliver clean water, sustain environmental flows, and provide multiple ecosystems, economic, and social services simultaneously. Water Europe advocates for hybrid strategy to address the challenges of aging water infrastructure and the impacts of climate change by combining the benefits of traditional engineered 'grey' infrastructure with nature-based 'green' solutions and 'smart' technologies.

Research infrastructures like those provided by Co-UDlabs are central to advancing these integrated approaches. They support the development and validation of both conventional and green-blue systems, and provide environments for experimentation with digital water technologies. These include smart monitoring, real-time data analysis, and AI-driven modeling to better understand long-term performance, asset deterioration, and climate change adaptation. Asset management practices — such as condition assessments, rehabilitation planning, and predictive maintenance — are being strengthened through RI-supported research. Moreover, the infrastructure must be dynamic enough to support ongoing educational programs and interdisciplinary collaboration, fostering a new generation of professionals capable of delivering resilient and sustainable urban drainage solutions.

The future of urban drainage will be shaped by the successful integration of technical infrastructure, environmental design, and digital innovation. RIs must be developed with long-term vision, avoiding fragmentation and redundancy through strategic coordination across Europe. Mapping and inventorying RIs at the EU level could facilitate collaboration and optimize investment. Ultimately, by enabling real-world testing, data generation, and knowledge exchange, Co-UDlabs and similar RIs serve as engines of transformation—driving a shift toward smart, sustainable, and integrated urban water systems.

Accessibility and dissemination: Improving accessibility to RIs is essential for maximizing their impact and fostering innovation. This involves not only encouraging the use of existing infrastructures but also increasing end-users interest in emerging technologies and methods. Dissemination experts are needed to ensure that relevant information reaches the industry and professionals effectively. Communicating in the native language of each country can significantly enhance understanding and application, thus broadening the utilization of RIs.

At the European level, a considerable number of practitioners are not fluent in international English, which presents a barrier to knowledge transfer and mobility. However, local collaborations can contribute meaningfully to European discussions through research networks, helping to bridge this language gap and enhancing collaborative efforts.

The Co-UDlabs network has experimented with various strategies to encourage collaboration and engagement. These include hackathons, open calls, team selection processes, and funding for research missions. Despite these initiatives, active engagement remains limited, particularly among practitioners outside research and development departments. Many professionals lack the authority to experiment with technical solutions beyond their immediate scope, which restricts their participation in these collaboration opportunities.

To address these challenges and knowledge sharing, Co-UDlabs has also implemented a range of learning activities, such as in-person training sessions, webinars, and workshops. However, participation in these activities is often deprioritized by researchers due to the specialized skills required in pedagogy and public engagement. Additionally, limited financial and logistical resources for attending conferences or exhibitions continue to pose a barrier, highlighting the need for further institutional support.

At the national level, there is a clear need to re-educate end-users about the availability and utility of RIs to ensure that research is grounded in real-world needs. At the same time, it is crucial to stimulate interest in nascent and emerging technologies. One key barrier to increasing usage is the generally low visibility of many RIs beyond their immediate networks. To overcome this, RI owners could proactively share equipment inventories and contribute to comprehensive European-scale RI mapping — an effort already initiated within Co-UDlabs. Such mapping could evolve into a catalogue of upcoming projects, open spaces, or shared facilities, significantly improving collaboration opportunities.

Access to RIs empowers interdisciplinary teams, including researchers, technical industries, and utility companies, who might not otherwise have access to practical testing resources. Importantly, it also serves to inform stakeholders that such networks and resources exist and are open for collaboration.

Policy and Regulation: The relationship between policy and science in the urban drainage sector is inherently complex, with scientific insights not always transmitted clearly, communicated or appropriately reflected in regulation. This disconnect can delay the implementation of innovative solutions and limit the flexibility needed to adapt to emerging challenges. There is a need for future-ready policies that support the development of research infrastructures and integrate circular economy principles. Independent validation and scientific endorsement of new technologies are also essential to build confidence within the industry and accelerate uptake.

Research infrastructures can inform policy by generating robust, evidence-based data that supports better decision-making. They allow for testing and demonstration of innovations at a pilot scale, helping to build trust in new solutions before wider adoption. Activities such as those undertaken within Co-UDlabs may contribute to standardizing methodologies across Europe and addressing knowledge gaps in areas like CSO management. These efforts enhance understanding of system performance and provide practical tools that can shape public policy and regulatory frameworks (Anta et al., 2025).

Despite this potential, current regulations often lag scientific progress. Policies and recommended practices may become outdated, and implementation may lack the technical clarity or financial support necessary to be effective. Communication barriers between researchers and policymakers further complicate the translation of research into practice, and the complexity of stormwater regulations in some countries makes them inaccessible to non-specialists. These challenges can hinder the broader application of sustainable solutions developed within research projects.

To strengthen the link between research and policy, there is a clear opportunity to foster collaboration between researchers, policymakers, utilities, and industry actors. Encouraging pilot projects, promoting case studies, and using existing networks to disseminate practical knowledge can improve awareness and uptake. Regulations must also be adaptable and reflect the latest scientific insights. Raising awareness among national regulators and supporting EU-level initiatives such as JCUD's working groups or UDRAIN can enhance coordination and help transition from research to real-world implementation.

Collaboration, User Engagement, and Visibility: Maximizing the impact of RIs requires deliberate efforts to foster collaboration and engage end-users more directly. In the urban drainage sector, water operators and technical

stakeholders often operate in silos, with limited exposure to broader RI networks or opportunities for joint innovation. This disconnection can prevent them from accessing valuable resources and technologies that could support more efficient, sustainable practices. RI projects should therefore place users at the center of their strategy, actively involving them in the development, testing, and implementation of solutions. Building trust and long-term relationships with practitioners is essential, particularly when it comes to high-cost infrastructure that demands clear use cases, defined objectives, and tangible benefits. Sharing data on long-term system performance, economic feasibility, and social value can strengthen decision-making and encourage buy-in from utilities, municipalities, and industry.

At the same time, visibility and awareness are critical for effective engagement. Many stakeholders do not know where to find relevant RIs or how these infrastructures could help address their specific challenges. This lack of visibility limits collaboration and slows down innovation uptake. Increasing awareness of available resources, tools, and expertise must be a core objective of RI projects. This includes creating accessible inventories, publishing user-friendly documentation, and developing training and communication materials tailored to different audiences. Public education also plays a key role in broadening understanding of sustainable urban drainage systems and the value RIs bring to their development. Initiatives such as open days, community workshops, or targeted campaigns can help demystify technical work and demonstrate real-world impact.

3.2. Adoption of Knowledge and Technologies from TA Activities

One of the main objectives of Co-UDlabs is to facilitate the adoption of innovation in both traditional buried pipe systems and blue-green infrastructures. This is achieved by increasing the understanding of asset deterioration and improving system resilience. The TA program is a direct instrument to achieve this goal by providing access to top-tier research infrastructures to develop, enhance, and demonstrate new concepts.

The success of the TA calls, with a significant number of proposals received and projects funded, indicates a demand and a potential for the adoption of the results of these projects (Anta, Naves, Ciambra, Tait, et al., 2024). The progress of the TA projects was monitored to verify progress in setting up the accesses and reported in D5.2 and D5.3. This helped ensure that the projects were carried out effectively and that their results can be considered for adoption (Anta et al., 2022; Anta, Naves, Ciambra, & Puertas, 2024).

The adoption of knowledge and technologies derived from the TA activities within the Co-UDlabs project is encouraged through various mechanisms and is intrinsically linked to the project's objectives.

Outreach and Participation Events: As part of its broader dissemination and engagement strategy, Co-UDlabs has placed significant emphasis on outreach and participation events designed to promote awareness of the TA program, foster collaboration, and build a vibrant international community around urban drainage research. These events have played a vital role in informing potential users about the program's objectives, available research infrastructures, and application procedures, while also serving as forums for idea exchange, networking, and the generation of new collaborative research projects.

Introductory webinars have been a key tool in this process. The first TA Call Webinar, held on October 13, 2021, introduced the Co-UDlabs initiative, its scope and goals, and provided a detailed overview of the TA program and the unique research facilities available. The event was well received, attracting over 150 registrations and a peak attendance of more than 100 participants from 36 countries, including representatives from small and medium-sized enterprises. The recording of this session was made available online to ensure continued access to its content. Building on this momentum, a second introductory webinar was held on June 20, 2023, to promote the launch of

the second TA call. This session aimed to reach an even broader and more diverse audience, including potential applicants from underrepresented regions. A total of 51 individuals participated, and the recording was made available on the Co-UDlabs YouTube channel (@coudlabs3583) to facilitate further outreach (Anta, Naves, Ciambra, & Puertas, 2024; Anta, Naves, Ciambra, Tait, et al., 2024).

Complementing these webinars, Co-UDlabs also organized two online Hackathon events, designed to increase accessibility to the project's research infrastructures and foster innovation within the multidisciplinary urban water community. The first Hackathon, held on November 23 and 25, 2021, created a collaborative online environment where participants could explore and refine their project ideas, build partnerships, and engage with the community. Twelve participants contributed fourteen project idea presentations, many of which were developed into full TA proposals. This event also led to the establishment of the Co-UDlabs Ideas Marketplace, a platform for ongoing collaboration and idea sharing. The second Hackathon, organized on September 6, 2023, offered a similar opportunity just one month before the second TA call deadline. Participants were able to present their proposals and receive constructive feedback from peers, academics, industry experts, and facility providers. This session attracted new participants from a diverse range of countries, including Belgium, Canada, Estonia, Germany, Serbia, and Sweden. As an incentive, the team with the most promising presentation was awarded a visit to the STREET facility at UDC, one of the Co-UDlabs research installations (Anta et al., 2023; Anta, Naves, Ciambra, Tait, et al., 2024).

Co-UDlabs has actively strengthened the visibility and reach of its TA program through participation in major international conferences and the organization of dedicated workshops. A notable example is the online Workshop on Urban Drainage Practice and Research Needs, hosted by IKT in November 2021, which introduced the first TA call to a largely non-academic audience. This was followed by a TA Workshop held during the Novatech 2023 international conference in Lyon, France which marked the official launch of the second TA call, provided information on the application process, and showcased preliminary results from the first funded projects. Further expanding its outreach, Co-UDlabs organized a special session at the International ICUD 2024 to present the project's core activities and highlight the success of its TA program, which over nearly three years has granted free access to 17 research infrastructures, while also contributing to the consolidation of an international urban drainage research community (Anta et al., 2023; Anta, Naves, Ciambra, Tait, et al., 2024).

Throughout all these outreach efforts, Co-UDlabs has placed special emphasis on digital communication, recognizing its importance in ensuring accessibility and inclusiveness. Webinars and virtual events have allowed geographically dispersed participants to engage with the project's activities, while the Co-UDlabs website, social media channels, and newsletters have served as central communication platforms. These channels are regularly updated with news, success stories, and outcomes from the TA program, ensuring that the community remains informed and actively connected.

Dissemination of Results: Dissemination of results generated through TA is a fundamental element of the Co-UDlabs project. It is not only a condition of participation for user groups but also a strategic mechanism to ensure that the knowledge produced is made available to a wide range of stakeholders. Co-UDlabs is strongly committed to maximizing the visibility, accessibility, and societal benefit of the research conducted across its network of research infrastructures.

To achieve this, the project promotes a comprehensive and integrated dissemination strategy that supports TA users in sharing their results through multiple, complementary channels. A major component of this strategy involves the publication of research outcomes in scientific journals and conference proceedings. providing users

with opportunities to reach wider audiences and engage directly with experts, practitioners, and policymakers (Anta, Naves, Ciambra, Tait, et al., 2024).

In addition to publications, Co-UDlabs supports open data sharing by encouraging users to upload their raw and processed datasets to repositories such as Zenodo. This enables other researchers and professionals to build upon the data and fosters a collaborative and transparent research environment (Anta, Naves, Ciambra, Tait, et al., 2024).

Another key dissemination avenue involves the production of technical reports and project deliverables that include summaries and analyses of TA project results. These documents are made publicly available through the project's website and platforms like Zenodo, ensuring that the insights gained are accessible to the wider community. To further broaden outreach, Co-UDlabs develops concise and visually engaging factsheets that describe selected TA projects. These materials include project summaries, photographs, and testimonials from participating researchers, and are distributed both online and at key events.

Interaction with Industry and the Non-Academic Sector: A central objective of Co-UDlabs has been to encourage and strengthen the engagement of industry and the non-academic sector, mobilizing their participation in both research activities and the dissemination and application of results. The project has placed particular emphasis on creating opportunities for utilities, regulators, SMEs, and private sector partners to contribute to and benefit from the TA program.

The involvement of personnel from non-academic institutions in research proposals, as well as targeted outreach to industry, has been essential to promoting the adoption of the knowledge and technologies developed through Co-UDlabs in practical and operational settings. These user groups have contributed to a diverse range of activities, including the testing of novel monitoring technologies, the exploration of new approaches to pipe rehabilitation, and the inspection and assessment of critical urban drainage infrastructure. Their participation has not only added practical relevance to the research conducted but has also opened avenues for translating scientific insights into operational improvements and commercial innovation.

Participation in the TA program offered significant benefits for many non-academic users. Gaining access to cutting-edge research infrastructures and expert support allowed them to test and validate innovative technologies that would have been difficult to evaluate independently. Collaborating with academic institutions also helped companies and practitioners stay up to date with the latest scientific developments and apply new knowledge in their work. These partnerships reduced the perceived risks of innovation by offering independent, research-backed validation of new tools and approaches. SMEs, in particular, benefited from the program's support for pilot testing and early-stage development—resources that would otherwise have been out of reach (Anta et al., 2023; Anta, Naves, Ciambra, Tait, et al., 2024).

The project has highlighted the importance of dedicated networking activities to involve and train actors beyond traditional drainage stakeholders, including technicians, municipal staff, and citizens. Looking forward, Co-UDlabs plans to further adapt its outreach formats and communication materials to better address the needs, expectations, and challenges faced by non-academic stakeholders, ensuring that the impact of the TA program extends across the full spectrum of the urban water management community.

3.3. Training and Education Activities

Co-UDlabs has organized a range of training activities targeting both early-stage researchers and industry professionals. These initiatives fostered knowledge transfer between the research community and practitioners, further strengthening links with existing communities in the urban drainage sector. Events such as the European

Junior Scientists Workshops (EJSW 2022 and 2024) have also offered valuable opportunities for networking and creating links among participants (De Nale & Guilloteau, 2024).

Through its diverse and comprehensive training and education program, Co-UDlabs actively promotes a culture of cooperation between research infrastructures and the wider urban drainage community. These activities are designed not only to share scientific outcomes but also to ensure the uptake and implementation of innovative technologies by a broad range of stakeholders.

Training Activities for Early-Stage and Junior Researchers: For early-stage and junior researchers, Co UDlabs has implemented a series of activities aimed at promoting training and networking within the field of UDS. Two early-stage researcher seminars were organized within the consortium. These events, targeting PhD students and early-career researchers from partner institutions, aimed to enhance interactions, share research ideas, and promote standardized experimental protocols (De Nale & Gryson, 2025). The first seminar took place in A Coruña, Spain, in June 2022, and focused on sediment accumulation, turbidity monitoring in wastewater systems, performance assessment in UDS, flood-related health risks, and the use of LIDAR and Structure-from-Motion (SfM) techniques for surveying and experimental planning. The second event, a workshop on “Post-PhD Career Opportunities in Urban Drainage”, was held on 19-20 September at the University of Sheffield. It featured speakers from both academia and industry, covering topics such as commercial product development, industrial and academic career pathways, innovation implementation, and funding.

The EJSW has proven to be an effective format for young scientists, promoting knowledge sharing, networking, and skill development through various interactive and hands-on sessions. High attendance and positive feedback highlight their success. The 25th edition of the EJSW was held in France in May 2022 and focused on monitoring urban drainage systems and rivers. This event included oral presentations and short courses covering topics such as low-cost monitoring solutions and uncertainty assessment. The event also included a workshop on ethics in science and research, highlighting the importance of responsible research conduct. Furthermore, participants engaged in hands-on training sessions across four afternoons (De Nale & Guilloteau, 2024).

The 26th edition of the EJSW held in May/June 2024 explored sewer process modeling, among other themes, and featured practical workshops covering various monitoring techniques such as large-scale PIV using drones images, RFID stone tracking, and use of geophones for sediment transport monitoring. Additional highlights included a guided geological field tour and sessions on open data sharing and scientific ethics. The event received enthusiastic feedback, with participants praising its hands-on focus, collaborative spirit, and balanced schedule. This multifaceted format proved highly effective in blending theoretical knowledge with applied training.

In addition, Aalborg University in Denmark hosted a 5-ECTS PhD course on sewer processes from October 7 to 11, 2024. The course provided advanced training on modeling microbial and chemical processes in sewer systems, focusing on practical applications for wastewater infrastructure. Key topics included new modeling tools, the WATS sewer process model, and experimental methods for assessing wastewater quality. Participants gained hands-on experience with numerical models and learned to predict and mitigate impacts from hazardous gases like hydrogen

Training Activities for UD Industry Professionals and Practitioners: Co-UDlabs has also developed training initiatives for urban drainage professionals, including stakeholders, regulators, and practitioners. These activities have been structured using various formats to respond to different learning preferences, balancing theoretical content with practical applications. Several workshops have been organized, beginning with an online workshop on urban drainage practice and research needs hosted by IKT in November 2021. This session sought to identify good practices and research gaps for optimizing urban drainage assets and improving system resilience. In November

2022, Deltares hosted an industrial workshop focused on determining flow rates in pumping stations and hydraulic structures, targeting professionals involved in the design, construction, and management of wastewater pressure systems. In March 2024, INSA and GRAIE co-organized a face-to-face 2-day workshop on uncertainty assessment in urban drainage monitoring data, introducing practitioners participants to the Urban Drainage Metrology Toolbox (UDMT) software tool (Anta, Naves, Ciambra, Tait, et al., 2024). Looking ahead, EAWAG lead a workshop on January 2025 on FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) data practices in urban drainage. This workshop explored the latest concepts, implementations, and resources aimed at harmonizing and sharing data to enhance urban drainage water management strategies.

In parallel, applied courses further supported industry engagement. An applied course on urban drainage metrology was conducted by UDC from July to September 2024, targeting professionals interested in measuring hydraulic and water quality parameters. Training activities also prominently featured the UDMT, developed by INSA Lyon, which was used in various workshops and courses to promote improved metrology practices. For instance, UDC led a session on the UDMT during the Spanish Water Engineering Days in 2023, leveraging an existing professional event to reach a broader audience (De Nale & Gryson, 2025). These training activities have shown the value of strategic coordination with ongoing industry events and the importance of aligning training with current professional needs.

Moreover, the workshop in early 2025 on “Key findings from Co-UDlabs research and where to access them” utilised findings from TA projects to illustrate how the outputs from the three Co-UDlabs Joint Research Activities were directly connecting research outcomes and practical applications in the field. In this event each of the leaders of the JRA’s presented the key findings from these tasks and Co-UDlabs staff presented on selected relevant TA projects they were involved in.

Public Webinars on Specific and Emerging Monitoring Techniques: Public webinars served as another effective channel to disseminate knowledge on emerging monitoring techniques in urban drainage. These online events were designed for both researchers and practitioners and addressed a variety of specialized topics. Examples include webinars on acoustic monitoring of suspended solids, routine uncertainty assessment in urban drainage data, the use of optical and computer vision techniques for flow and process measurements, and Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy chemical mapping. These webinars attracted high registration and participation levels, reflecting strong interest across the community. To extend the reach of these sessions beyond their live format, recordings were made available on the Co-UDlabs YouTube channel (@coudlabs3583). Additionally, proactive promotion through social media channels helped broaden awareness and accessibility, contributing to the project's inclusive approach to dissemination (De Nale & Gryson, 2025).

These training activities facilitated knowledge transfer and skills development. They contributed directly to bridging the gap between research and implementation by supporting the adoption of new monitoring devices, enhancing metrology practices, and promoting sustainable stormwater management solutions. Furthermore, Co-UDlabs emphasized the importance of interdisciplinary education in urban drainage by integrating perspectives from engineering, environmental sciences, urban planning, and social sciences. Continuous professional development has been emphasized as essential to ensure that practitioners stay updated with the latest innovations and techniques.

4. Strategy for the consolidation on a European Urban Drainage Research Infrastructures Community

During the 3rd General Assembly of Co-UDlabs at EAWAG, in January 22-24, 2024, Co-UDlabs partners prioritized from a set of about ten Key Exploitable Results three of them to be worked out in a Horizon Result Booster workshop held in February 2024 with the consultants. One of the selected results to be exploited was the development of a Strategic agenda on urban drainage research infrastructures. Based on the work done for the workshop, using the feedback from the consultants and the identification of needs of such community and lessons learned during the development of the project, we draft in this section a strategy for the consolidation in the long-term of an urban drainage RIs community.

4.1. Context

In Europe, many universities, water utilities, and their supply chains have advanced some large-scale facilities and field facilities, but there is a lack of awareness about these resources, especially across borders. This means potential users don't know which RIs or how to benefit from them. Researchers and industrial developers often feel unsure about using large RIs because there aren't many examples showing their benefits. Additionally, these infrastructures aren't organized in a way that's easy for outsiders to access.

Collaborative projects within RIs aren't well-known in the field of urban drainage systems, leading to a lack of confidence in their outcomes. There's also a problem with sharing protocols and results, causing wasted time and resources as people search for information that might already be available. Language barriers further complicate collaboration, as many practitioners don't speak English.

Thus, creating a European network of research infrastructures can address these issues by improving awareness, accessibility, and collaboration, ultimately benefiting all stakeholders.

4.2. Vision and Objectives

Vision. The long-term strategic agenda developed through Co-UDlabs aims to build a cohesive community of urban drainage research infrastructures across Europe. By enhancing awareness, accessibility, and collaboration, it seeks to create a trusted network that facilitates innovative research and practical solutions for urban drainage challenges.

The **main objectives** of the agenda are:

- **Increase Awareness and Accessibility:** Promote the existence and benefits of research infrastructures (RI) among universities, water utilities, and their supply chains, and organize these RIs to be easily accessible to researchers and industrial developers.
- **Enhance Collaboration and Confidence:** Foster pooling of infrastructures, sharing of protocols and contribution to create new standards, while encouraging the end-user community to utilize large RIs by showcasing successful case studies and experiences.
- **Expand Funding and Overcome Barriers:** Develop mechanisms to support collaborative research and innovation in urban drainage, combining public and private funding sources, and integrate working groups from different countries and EU water associations, addressing linguistic differences.

4.3. Proposed Actions for Strengthening the Network

According to the main objectives described above, three main group of tasks or core activities are planned as follows:

1. **Develop a Comprehensive RI Catalogue of facilities and services.** Create and maintain a global catalogue of services, facilities, and contacts, ensuring that the catalogue is easily accessible and regularly updated to reflect new additions and changes. This catalogue may include not just the facilities, but also other aspects, such as the training and standardization services to be addressed. We aim to provide a global catalogue of services and facilities and contacts. More than a marketplace, a trusted community.
2. **Enhancing knowledge exchange and best practices.** Implement EU training programs, summer courses, and short courses tailored to national languages and the needs of practitioners. Host seminars, short conferences, create and get involved in working groups to discuss practical problems and promote joint activities. Expand collaboration with external partners and integration of activities.
3. **Establish Funding Mechanisms and Collaborative Projects.** Identify and secure public and private funding opportunities for collaborative research and innovation. Facilitate transnational access programs and sponsorships to support the use of RIs by researchers and industrial developers.

4.4. Consolidation of a catalogue of services and facilities in the field of urban drainage

Co-UDlabs partners launched the creation of a catalogue of services and facilities which can be provided worldwide in the field of UDS. Several attempts to create inventories of water related infrastructures and living labs were developed in the past by Water Europe, and more recently by the Water4all consortium.

The creation of the Water Europe Atlas of Water-Oriented Living Labs (WOLLS) was a significant initiative aimed at mapping and understanding innovation ecosystems within the water sector. The first edition of the atlas, published in 2019, identified 105 WOLLS across Europe (Water Europe, 2019). This mapping exercise followed and applied the rationale of Water Europe's Water Vision and its Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda. The identified WOLLS were categorized by country and their use-context, such as agricultural, urban, industrial, and ecosystem, reflecting Water Europe's strategic priorities.

Following the initial mapping, Water Europe released further publications to delve deeper into the WOLL concept and methodology. These included three Water-Oriented Living Labs Notebooks series dealing with the elaboration on a methodology to establish, compare and assess different Living Labs (Water4all, 2024).

In the framework of Water4all partnership, Water Europe and Water4all performed and update of the 2019 atlas (Water4all, 2024). The 2024 edition of the atlas employed the methodology proposed in the notebook series to select and evaluate featured WOLLS. While the first edition identified 105 WOLLS, the provided excerpts from the 2024 atlas detail profiles of selected 24 WOLLS. Based on these profiles, at least six WOLLS appear to have a focus, or activities related to urban drainage systems in a manner that could align with the work of projects like Co-UDlabs.

Another initiative promoted by Water4all is the creation of a catalogue of Research Infrastructures according to the definition of Research Infrastructures promoted by the EU, in the sense that are facilities that provide resources and services for research communities to conduct research and foster innovation. As mentioned in Section 2.3, Co-UDlabs was included in the catalogue of water related research infrastructures¹, but a search within the 94 entries provided just one infrastructure related with wastewater treatment.

Thus, there is a need to create an atlas of RIs describing facilities and services in the field of urban drainage systems. As stated before, this will be accomplished through the Working Group UDRAIN on Large Research Infrastructures. By November 2024, the core group of UDRAIN was formalized, establishing a leadership board composed of:

- Chair: Jose Anta – University of A Coruña
- Co-Chair: Kelsey Flanagan – Luleå Technical University
- Secretary: James Shucksmith – University of Sheffield
- Co-Secretary: Marius Møller Rokstad – NTNU – Norwegian University of Science and Technology
- YWP Representative: Jakob Benisch – TU Dresden

UDRAIN is driven by clear, strategic objectives:

- **Create a global inventory (Atlas) of large-scale RIs in urban drainage** to improve visibility, access, and collaboration. And provisory version of the atlas is presented in the Annex 1. The Atlas will be updated at least once a year, each time the working group meets, during the 5 years after the end of Co-UDlabs.
- **Promote technical cooperation and knowledge sharing** among RI managers, researchers, practitioners, SMEs, and regulators.
- **Facilitate transnational access to research infrastructures**, following the successful model of the Co-UDlabs project.
- **Standardise data collection, research protocols, and training activities.**
- **Foster mutual learning and innovation**, ensuring that infrastructure research supports real-world needs and societal challenges in urban drainage.

UDRAIN will be also an opportunity to foster the consolidation of Co-UDlabs results after the end of the project, by establishing at least one annual meetings in which we can track project results.

4.5. Enhancing Knowledge Exchange and Best Practices

Through Networking Activities (NAs), Co-UDlabs aimed to develop complementary capacities among the participating RIs and strengthen the European research community. The coordination of JRAs further fine-tuned these synergies and highlighted the complementarities of the involved RIs. For instance, WP2's efforts in harmonization were intended to make data sharing and reuse much easier across the Co-UDlabs RIs, establishing a best practice for data management. Staff mobility activities were designed to facilitate the exchange of best practices and know-how among the staff operating the different RIs, leading to improved quality and services

At WP3, Co-UDlabs partners organized training workshops, webinars, and in-person seminars that often showcased the capabilities and best practices in utilizing the Co-UDlabs RIs. These events targeted various audiences, including early-stage researchers who would be future users of RIs, and practitioners who could benefit from accessing advanced research facilities. The promotion of remote sensing techniques and other advanced methods through these training activities aimed to increase the effective use of RI resources (De Nale & Gryson, 2025).

One of the main challenges related to the consolidation of training and harmonization activities is related to the funding which will be discussed in section 4.6. Another key topic is related to the activities of promotion and integration of different participants in the framework of the community of Urban Drainage RIs.

There is a need to expand the collaboration of the different RIs owners with external partners. Projects and research activities must be organized with a holistic perspective which engages to the majority of UDS actors at each level, involving, the following processes:

- identifying issues and determining research and development needs,
- developing project ideas and research proposals,
- identifying and involving suitable project partners,
- determining the required budget and acquiring funding,
- implementing research and development projects, and
- disseminating and implementing project results.

To achieve the best possible acceptance of new innovative solutions and to achieve the widest possible impact of research results, it is important to expand collaboration with external partners and to involve the following stakeholders of the water sector with the focus on urban drainage in these processes, in addition to the universities and research institutes which represents the **academia**:

- **Asset owners and water utilities:** Asset owners and utilities are water companies, municipalities or water management associations that operate sewerage systems and their assets. Depending on how the wastewater disposal is organized nationally, these are either private or public companies. They are responsible for wastewater and rainwater disposal. This means that they have not only to organise management and maintenance of these assets to ensure a proper wastewater and stormwater disposal, but also to implement new and innovate solutions to meet the challenges of the future. They are obliged to act in the public interest, and thus also to protect the environment and the citizens. For these reasons, these stakeholders have a very special significance.
- **Industry:** In this case, the group of industries includes manufacturers and suppliers of products, materials and technical and organizational solutions and services for UD. They are selling their products and solutions to asset owners and utilities. However, they also have a great interest in the development of new products and solutions to increase sales and to be able to assert themselves in the market. However, according to this definition, the group of industries also includes service companies that work on behalf of operators on the network (e.g. sewer cleaning, sewer rehabilitation, new construction, planning, ...).
- **Professional (umbrella) organisation for urban drainage:** These organisations bundle interest of asset owners/utilities or industry or both. They represent the interests e. g. towards politics, regulators. These organisations could be organized internationally like IWA, EWA or nationally like RIONED Foundation (Stichting RIONED) in the Netherlands, VLARIO in Belgium or DWA in Germany.
- **Politics and authorities:** This group is responsible for water legislation and monitoring of its implementation. To support implementation, politics and authorities also develops funding programs for asset owners / utilities, industry and science, to foster new and innovative technical and organisational solutions.

In addition to the stakeholders listed above, there are other stakeholders, such as citizens and environmental organizations. For example, involving citizens in research projects on the topic of property drainage, public relations, etc. can also be useful in achieving research goals.

A fundamental question is how academia (universities and research institutes) can interact and engage with the various stakeholders. For example, there is the possibility of involving the stakeholders in an institutionalized form in the work of the scientific institution. A permanent research advisory board made up of industry and asset owners/utilities can support research and development in an advisory capacity by identifying research needs, providing some of the research funding needed in the form of crowd funding, or representing the interests of the research institution vis-à-vis other stakeholders (decision makers, public funding agencies, standardization bodies). In addition, networking and the associated commitment of the research institution's employees are important for organizing research and obtaining input from the various stakeholders for research and development.

However, the option of bringing the various stakeholders together in the context of specific research and development projects appears to be almost more important. Only through concrete cooperation in the context of projects can the knowledge and practical experience of the various stakeholders be combined and, in this way, targeted questions be addressed. However, networking among employees and/or a corresponding research advisory board (see above) can certainly simplify the process of organizing such projects, since contact with stakeholders is already in place and thus the initiation of such projects is simplified. At this point, it should be noted that the asset owners/utilities play a special role in many application-oriented research questions in urban drainage. Asset owners / utilities should implement research and development results in their network in a very specific way to improve wastewater disposal and meet the challenges of the future. It is therefore recommended that these projects be geared to the needs of the asset owners / utilities.

The Transnational Access project Assessment of Inspection Tools for Rising (AIR) mains as part of Co-UDlabs (see report in page 110 of the Deliverable 9.1 of the project – Puertas et al., 2023) can be mentioned as a very instructive example of the project-related integration of various stakeholders in a specific issue. In this project, “science”, “network operators” or “organizations/umbrella organizations” and “industry” stakeholders were specifically involved. The project was made possible by the “politics/authorities” stakeholders through the EU as a funding body.

The AIR project is concerned with the question of which methods can be used to identify defects in wastewater pressure pipes. This is because a conventional inspection using TV inspection, as is the case with gravity sewers, is generally not possible with wastewater pressure pipes due to the boundary conditions. So other inspection methods are needed to identify defects on time.

Figure 5 TA AIR project structure and model of a process-oriented quality improvement system (based on ISO 9001).

This question was defined by a group of asset owners / utilities managed by the RIONED Foundation. The RIONED Foundation (Stichting RIONED) is a Dutch umbrella organization for water management that represents the interests of Dutch asset owners / utilities (see Figure 5). Under the leadership of RIONED and with the participation of the Dutch municipality of Arnhem and the British water companies Wessex Water, Yorkshire Water, Severn Trent and United Utilities, the requirements for testing the inspection techniques to be investigated were defined based on their own practical experience in operating wastewater pressure pipes. They defined the test set-up and the defects to be identified. On this basis, a test set-up was constructed in the IKT's large-scale test facility. Within Co-UDlabs, IKT took on the role of research service provider, ensuring access to the lab for the project, including measurements and scientific assistance. Subsequently, the various innovative inspection systems from industry, based on ultrasonic and acoustic techniques, were tested for their performance and compared with each other. In addition, proprietary developments by research institutions (in this case, the University of Bristol and the University of Sheffield) were also examined in terms of their performance. As a result, the asset owners / utilities received information about the performance of the inspection systems and their application limits.

In principle, this results in a cycle of product improvement and optimization (Figure 5) which may also trigger new developments. If the manufacturers want to remain competitive in the market, they are increasingly forced, after the investigations have been completed, to further improve their products in line with the requirements of the network operators or to develop new products in a targeted manner. This results in a “product improvement cycle” with a constant improvement in the quality of the connection systems.

4.6. Establishing new funding mechanisms after Horizon 2020 INFRAIA Starting Communities

The former Horizon 2020 INFRAIA (Integrating Activities for Advanced Communities) call aimed to support the integration and accessibility of research infrastructures across Europe. The call was divided into two main categories: i) Starting Communities and Advanced Communities, and ii) Starting Communities were focused on integrating research infrastructures that have not previously received EU funding, mobilizing comprehensive

consortia of key research infrastructures and stakeholders from different Member States and Associated Countries. These projects supported transnational and virtual access for European researchers, cooperation between research infrastructures, and joint research activities. On the other hand, Advanced Communities aimed to further integrate and enhance existing research infrastructures that have already established substantial networking and coordination, covered a wide range of scientific fields and emphasized user needs, providing new or advanced research infrastructure services, and fostering innovation through partnerships with industry.

Co-UDlabs was funded under the last Horizon 2020 INFRAIA call and exemplified what the EC expected by a Starting Community. Co-UDlabs brought together a consortium of universities and research institutions specialised in urban drainage, integrated a set of activities of research and innovation in urban drainage systems to address critical challenges such as population growth, climate change, and threats to public health caused by emerging pollutants and pathogens, provided access to 17 unique RIs, offered training and access to advanced scientific instruments, smart monitoring technologies, and digital water analysis tools. Despite its initial aspirations to grow into an Advanced Community, the current INFRA programme of the Horizon Europe limits the availability of consortia as Co-UDlabs to established themselves as a network of large RIs as the Advanced Community call no longer exists, and the new Horizon Europe – INFRA funding programme includes as a requirement that at least one partner consortium is part of European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC) or the European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI).

Thus, the Horizon 2020 program has played a crucial role in funding and developing a wide array of RIs across Europe. These infrastructures have been instrumental in advancing scientific research and innovation. Over time, some of these RIs have evolved into more structured and sustainable entities, becoming a legal entity after a long-term processes which could take 10 or 15 years and being integrated into ERIC or part of ERIC or ESFRI roadmap. This transition has been driven by the need for greater integration, sustainability, and impact of research infrastructures.

Therefore, the current situation for establishing new funding mechanisms for a RIs network which involves UDS requires analysis of three main initiatives:

- The European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
- The European Research Infrastructure Consortium
- The Horizon Europe Infrastructure work program.

The ESFRI provides a strategic roadmap for the development of pan-European RIs, ensuring that they align with the long-term needs of the European Research Area (ERA). The ESFRI roadmap includes both new projects and existing RIs that have demonstrated their scientific excellence and strategic importance. ERICs, on the other hand, are legal entities that facilitate the establishment and operation of research infrastructures on a European scale. They provide a framework for member states to collaborate and share resources, ensuring the long-term sustainability and accessibility of RIs.

Based on the analysis of the current **ESFRI** landscape², there isn't a specific ESFRI Research Infrastructure that Co-UDlabs or, in broad terms, a network of urban water RIs could be directly included in at this moment. However,

² <https://landscape2024.esfri.eu>

there are potential indirect connections both with Data, Computing and Digital Research Infrastructures and with Environment domain of ESFRI, and possibilities for the future.

Within the Environment domain, existing ESFRI Landmarks and Projects focus on areas like the atmosphere (e.g., ACTRIS ERIC, ICOS ERIC), oceans (e.g., Euro-Argo ERIC, EMSO ERIC), biosphere, and integrated land-sea systems (e.g., DANUBIUS-RI, JERICO network). Unfortunately, there is no room for any RIs of urban drainage, or in broader terms, urban water system, to be easily adopted in the current framework of Environment cluster of ESFRI as in the Environment domain the built environment is not considered.

The same analysis was performed based on the information **ERICs** landscape³. There is no specific ERIC dedicated to urban drainage. However, several ERICs are related to water systems and environmental research, which could indirectly contribute to UD studies and solutions like ACTRIS ERIC (focused on atmospheric science, the data can be relevant for understanding precipitation patterns and their impact on urban drainage systems) or AnaEE (focused on the analysis and experiment of the ecosystems, with a relation to environmental impacts of urban drainage and develop sustainable management practices).

Lastly, the current **Horizon Europe Infrastructure work programme (2023-25)**⁴ builds on the successes of Horizon 2020 and aims to further enhance the landscape of European RIs. The main pillars of the INFRA programme include:

1. **Consolidation and Development:** This pillar focuses on supporting the integration and development of existing RIs to ensure they meet the evolving needs of the research community.
2. **Accessibility and Integration:** The programme promotes the opening of RIs to a broader range of users, including those from different scientific disciplines and geographical regions. This includes facilitating transnational and virtual access to these facilities, enabling researchers to utilize state-of-the-art equipment and resources regardless of their location.
3. **Policy and International Cooperation:** Emphasizing the importance of strong policy frameworks and international collaboration, this pillar aims to foster partnerships between European and global RIs. It seeks to enhance the exchange of knowledge and best practices, driving innovation and scientific excellence.
4. **Innovation and Training:** The programme supports activities that enhance the innovation potential of RIs, including the development of new technologies and methodologies. It also focuses on training and capacity-building, ensuring that researchers have the skills and knowledge needed to effectively use these infrastructures and contribute to cutting-edge research.

The program is structured around five destinations, summarized as follows:

1. **INFRADEV:** Aims to develop, consolidate, and optimise the European research infrastructures landscape and maintain global leadership.
2. **INFRAEOSC:** Focuses on enabling an operational, open, and FAIR EOSC ecosystem.
3. **INFRA SERV:** Concentrates on providing RI services to support health research, accelerate the green and digital transformation, and advance frontier knowledge.

³ https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-research-and-innovation/our-digital-future/european-research-infrastructures/eric/eric-landscape_en

⁴ https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/document/download/c49b49cf-3ad1-4392-a075-4e701505c113_en

4. **INFRATECH:** Deals with the development of the next generation of scientific instrumentation, tools, methods, and advanced digital solutions for RIs.
5. **INFRAJET:** Focuses on providing network connectivity in research and education to enable collaboration without boundaries

Within the 2023-25 work programme, Co-UDlabs partners were focused on the construction and consolidation of the *Starting Community*. In 2025, a new work programme will be released in May with new funding opportunities. Co-UDlabs partners will analyse the work programme and prepare to apply for funding. This will require a shift from the initial strategy of being consolidated through an Advanced Community, as outlined in the current Horizon Europe Infrastructure programme. In some calls (especially thus intended to provide Transnational Access), the consortium may need to include an ERIC or ESFRI entity, as the European Commission promotes of cross-disciplinary approaches.

Looking at cross-disciplinary approaches, the ESFRI landscape can serve as a basin to start looking for new funding schemes. For instance, in the field of Data, Computing and Digital Research Infrastructures ESFRI acknowledges the transformative potential of Digital Twins to unlock digital modeling by leveraging High-Performance Computing (HPC) and Artificial Intelligence (AI). This enables the simulation and study of complex phenomena in real time, enhancing research quality and fostering innovation to address global challenges like climate change.

Destination Earth⁵, a flagship initiative of the European Commission aiming to develop a highly accurate global-scale digital model of the Earth. This model will monitor, simulate and predict the interaction between natural phenomena and human activities. It will contribute to achieving the objectives of the transition towards green and digital as part of the European Commission's Green Deal.

According to the ESFRI roadmap, another initiative to track is the European Open Data Spaces⁶. As part of this strategy, common European data spaces are being established in several domains to increase data availability for use in the economy and society, while maintaining control over companies and individuals who generate data. Another initiative which the consortium will explore is related to the European Open Science Cloud⁷. The EOSC is a major initiative by the European Commission to create a federated and open multi-disciplinary environment where researchers, innovators, companies, and citizens can publish, find, and reuse data, tools, and services for research, innovation, and educational purposes. EOSC aims to develop a "Web of FAIR Data and Services" that integrates existing infrastructures, repositories, and tools across Europe, enhancing research productivity, innovation, and reproducibility

The consortium has also identified the OSCARS (Open Science Cluster for Advancing Research, <https://oscars-project.eu/>) projects as an initiative aimed at fostering the uptake of Open Science in Europe. These projects bring together world-class European RIs to promote FAIR data management practices. The OSCARS projects are part of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) initiative and focus on creating interdisciplinary FAIR data services and working practices.

The key objectives of OSCARS projects are

⁵ <https://destination-earth.eu/>

⁶ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/data-spaces>

⁷ <https://open-science-cloud.ec.europa.eu/>

1. **Consolidation of Science Clusters:** Integrate past achievements of various Science Clusters into lasting interdisciplinary FAIR data services.
2. **Development of Open Science Projects:** Through cascading grant mechanisms, involve a broad range of research communities in developing Open Science projects and services.
3. **Establishment of Competence Centres:** Create Community-based Competence Centres (CCCs) to align practices in scientific data analysis and support the EOSC initiative.

In the framework of OSCARs project, five Science Clusters⁸ and five CCCs⁹ linked to the clusters were created. The science clusters have grown out of five collaborative projects funded by the European Union in 2019 to link ESFRI and other world-class RIs to the EOSC. In the field of Environment, which is the most closely related cluster to Co-UDlabs, the **ENVRI Community**¹⁰ is the reference science cluster.

The ENVRI Community is a dynamic and collaborative network of European environmental research infrastructures, projects, and stakeholders dedicated to advancing the understanding of the Earth's complex systems. The ENVRI Community was established to create a cohesive network of environmental research infrastructures across Europe. The foundational project, ENVRI (2011-2014), laid the groundwork by bringing together various research facilities and fostering collaboration among scientists and researchers. This initial effort was followed by ENVRIplus (2015-2019), which aimed to integrate and enhance the capabilities of these infrastructures, creating a more unified and effective community.

One of the most significant projects within the ENVRI Community is ENVRI-FAIR (2019-2023). This initiative focused on aligning data management practices with the principles of FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable), ensuring that environmental data is more accessible and usable for researchers worldwide. By improving data sharing and interoperability, ENVRI-FAIR has made a substantial impact on the efficiency and effectiveness of environmental research. Looking ahead, the ENVRI Community continues to innovate with projects like ENVRINNOV (2024-2027), which is dedicated to fostering innovation within the environmental research community by leveraging new technologies and methodologies. Additionally, ENVRI-Hub NEXT (2024-2027) seeks to improve access to environmental data and services by incorporating next-generation digital solutions, further enhancing the community's capabilities.

The ENVRI Community encompasses a diverse range of RIs across four main environmental domains¹¹:

- The atmospheric domain focuses on the study of atmospheric processes, climate change, and air quality and has 7 RIs.
- The marine domain covers research related to marine ecosystems, oceanography, and marine biodiversity and has 8 RIs.
- The biodiversity – ecosystem domain involves the study of terrestrial ecosystems, biodiversity, and ecological processes through 7 RIs.

⁸ <https://science-clusters.eu/>

⁹ <https://oscar-project.eu/clusters-open-science-competence-centres>

¹⁰ <https://envri.eu/>

¹¹ <https://envri.eu/research-infrastructures/>

- The solid earth domain focuses on geophysical processes, geology, and the Earth's structure and accounts with 6 RIs.

Co-UDlabs could potentially be integrated into ENVRI Community. The potential areas of collaboration are related with data management and the application of FAIR principles. ENVRINNOV's focus on fostering innovation within environmental research can complement Co-UDlabs' efforts to develop smart monitoring technologies and digital water analysis tools. Training and capacity building are also crucial aspects of collaboration.

Finally, sustainable solutions are at the heart of both ENVRI and Co-UDlabs. Integrated solutions that address urban and environmental sustainability and research initiatives that explore the impact of urbanization on natural water systems, climate resilience, and other critical issues, leading to more effective and sustainable outcomes could be addressed through a collaborative framework in which Co-UDlabs RIs are integrated in ENVRI domain. This will probably involve move towards the consolidation of one or more RIs in ERIC domain.

The Co-UDlabs partners realized that the path to consolidating a research structure in an ERIC is not an easy one, but the aim of Co-UDlabs is to explore this way of working, which will be adequate to integrate some of the RIs present in the current consortium into a multidisciplinary research community such as the ENVRI community.

To explore possible collaboration with ENVRI Community UDC has started some initial conversations with Spanish representatives of ERIC

RIs and ENVRI community and more networking will be established at the European Geosciences Union General Assembly which will take place between April 27 and May 2 in Vienna, where Co-UDlabs will present its consortium in the Session Advancing Environmental Science through Integrated Research Infrastructures, organized by EC Research Executive Agency (REA) representatives.

Lastly, other funding opportunities which the consortium is exploring towards the consolidation of the capacity building work performed during the projects are the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA), in particular the ones designed to support doctoral education and staff exchange.

By participating in the MSCA Doctoral Networks¹², Co-UDlabs partners can provide high-quality doctoral training that integrates academic rigor with practical industry experience. The doctoral candidates will benefit from excellent supervision and mentorship, ensuring their research aligns with both scientific excellence and industry needs. Most of the consortium partners are eligible and remain beneficiaries within the consortium, ensuring the continuity of Co-UDlabs. Additionally, we have the opportunity to strengthen the consortium by incorporating new partners who can play a strategic role in training the next generation of urban drainage researchers. Importantly, the call is open to graduate students of any nationality, enabling students from Europe, associated countries, and third countries to benefit from this doctoral training opportunity.

The MSCA Staff Exchange Programme¹³ will further enhance knowledge transfer and collaboration between Co-UDlabs partners and other leading institutions and organizations across Europe. Furthermore, third countries may also participate, opening the Co-UDlabs initiative to global cooperation and strengthening its international dimension. By facilitating the mobility of researchers and staff, the programme will expose participants to diverse

¹² <https://marie-sklodowska-curie-actions.ec.europa.eu/actions/doctoral-networks>

¹³ <https://marie-sklodowska-curie-actions.ec.europa.eu/actions/staff-exchanges>

perspectives and expertise, fostering interdisciplinary collaboration and capacity building. The next call closes on October 8th, and we are currently evaluating the opportunity to participate.

Engaging in the MSCA Doctoral Networks and Staff Exchange Programme will also increase the international visibility of Co-UDlabs brand, fostering strategic partnerships with leading institutions and organizations. These collaborations will expand the network of Co-UDlabs, enabling it to tackle urban drainage challenges more effectively.

Furthermore, from the coordination unit, we will analyze other potential calls that could ensure the continuity of infrastructure access or foster the development of research projects on urban drainage between Co-UDlabs consortium partners and beyond utilizing the Co-UDlabs infrastructure. The delay in the publication of the 2025 Work Programmes has prevented the early identification of funding opportunities; however, we remain committed to actively seeking alternative options to support and expand the initiative.

5. Conclusions

The Co-UDlabs project has made significant progress in building a European community of research infrastructures (RIs) dedicated to urban drainage systems. By integrating 17 unique facilities and promoting collaboration through its Transnational Access (TA) programme, training activities, and stakeholder engagement, the project has laid the groundwork for a long-term, sustainable research and innovation network. Co-UDlabs has not only supported high-quality research and knowledge exchange but also demonstrated how RIs can act as key enablers of practical, scalable solutions to pressing urban water challenges.

A key achievement is the establishment of the **UDRAIN Working Group**, which seeks to create a global platform for RI collaboration, technical coordination, and visibility. This initiative, supported by a growing number of international institutions, reflects the momentum and interest generated by Co-UDlabs and offers a pathway to further consolidate its results and partnerships.

However, sustaining this momentum will require navigating new funding landscapes. With limited opportunities for Starting Communities under Horizon Europe, Co-UDlabs partners must now explore alternatives, including cross-disciplinary initiatives, alignment with ESFRI and ERIC frameworks, and participation in digital and environmental research programmes. Establishing Co-UDlabs as a trusted network within these evolving contexts will be critical for continued development.

Equally important is the need to maintain strong connections with users, particularly utilities, SMEs, and policymakers. Ensuring the visibility, accessibility, and relevance of RIs will depend on continued efforts to promote best practices, shared standards, and co-created solutions. Enhancing communication and reducing entry barriers—such as language or administrative complexity—will be essential to engage a broader and more diverse community

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Annex 1. UDRAIN Atlas.

Large Research Infrastructure in Urban Drainage UDRAIN

ATLAS

UDRAIN Working Group aims to establish the first global network of large research infrastructures focused on urban drainage systems. This initiative addresses the lack of coordination in Europe and worldwide, providing versatile and unique testing ground opportunities in laboratory conditions to improve knowledge, technology, and methods in urban water and drainage management.

Introduction

Research and innovation development in Urban Drainage Systems are closely linked to studying and testing new solutions and methods that water utilities, regulators, and practitioners can easily and extensively implement in urban systems.

However, water utilities are traditionally cautious innovation adopters, often requiring full- or near full-scale testing of novel solutions before implementing them. This makes it difficult to transfer new knowledge and technologies from research to the broader end-user community. It is key to consistently increase engagement and participation of companies, local regulators, and SMEs alongside researchers and practitioners. Interconnecting large-scale urban Research Infrastructure (RI) facilities while also actively creating multi-sectorial teams will make novel technology more efficient, faster, and safer.

Innovative technologies and the ‘hybrid grey-and-green infrastructure’ are “Key Components for a Water Smart Society” in the Strategic Innovation and Research Agenda (SIRA) of the Water Europe platform. So far, however, these have been tested primarily at pilot or small scale. UDRAIN, the JCUD Working Group on Large Research Infrastructures in Urban Drainage, would support a strategic transition from pilot/small scale to large-scale facilities implementation in urban drainage systems, making this process available to a larger and more diverse group of users within the urban drainage community.

Objectives and Scope

The UDRAIN Working Group aims to establish the first worldwide network of large Research Infrastructures (RI) of urban drainage systems. Interest in cooperation, technical collaboration, and joint initiatives such as transnational access programmes, training activities, and knowledge exchange has been rapidly growing for the past few years. The recent experience of H2020-INFRAIA project Co-UDlabs — with transnational access to 17 different large research facilities pooled together by seven partners in seven different European countries — is proof of the growing demand for such frameworks.

UDRAIN's main objectives and contribution, moreover, are also consistent with the strategic vision of several international organisations and relevant stakeholders in the fields of water management, conservation, drainage, and related urban infrastructure. In its Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA), Water4All — a Partnership in the framework of the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme — stresses the importance of horizontal coordination and peer-to-peer collaboration, with an emphasis on providing “an overall framework and coherent direction” and “aligning existing water Research and Innovation programmes”. The Strategy highlights the importance of “monitoring, evaluation and prediction tools... modelling tools... exposure, risk assessment procedures, health protection” as key tools towards water infrastructure resilience and security through “trans-boundary cooperation, policy integration, alignment and water policy coordination”. UDRAIN is addressing a lack of coordination across Europe and worldwide on these assets: large infrastructures provide a unique testing ground and versatile opportunities in lab conditions to improve knowledge, technology, and methods in water management and urban drainage.

To date, however, the ESFRI European Roadmap for research infrastructures does not include any facilities designed for urban drainage research, and large infrastructure networks are only minimally included in EU-funded research. Countries such as the United States and the United Kingdom have research infrastructure programmes designed to encourage the development of national research infrastructure and support collaborative, cutting-edge research. Collaborative infrastructures could benefit from enhanced international coordination worldwide to address challenges such as: a) common data collection and storage procedures; b) increase the operational sustainability and improvement of the catalogue of available services; and c) make the installations more consistent with the actual needs and objectives of their users.

In close collaboration with other well-established JCUD Working Groups — such as the International Working Group on Data and Models (IWGDM) or the Urban Drainage Asset Management (UDAM) working group — the UDRAIN working group wants to develop an improved cooperation roadmap, including research infrastructures worldwide. It aims to improve available services, especially by retrofitting existing infrastructure, and thus expand the range of possible uses, advanced training, and support to innovative research. The group, finally, would also seek viable options to consolidate such a network in more formal and institutionalised ways.

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Technological Center for Hydraulics (Centro Tecnológico de Hidráulica)

Name of Institution: University of Sao Paulo
Type of Institution: University;Research centre;
Level of Access: National

Country: Brazil
City: São Paulo
Cost of Access:On request

Other partners: FCTH - Fundação Centro Tecnológico de Hidráulica

Keywords: Hydrayulic works, sustainable drainage, water and waste water treatment, water resources monitoring

Thematic Area: Stormwater;Combined;

Description:

The laboratory is located in a 50,000m² area of the USP campus in the city of São Paulo, and has equipment for testing physical models, a water quality analysis laboratory, facilities for measuring equipment, approximately 500 hydrological monitoring stations and two meteorological radars used to develop forecast models. The team has 40 researchers and 70 support professionals.

Current Status: Active

Scale: Laboratory

Urban flooding

Runoff pollution

Performance of urban assets

SuDS solutions

Frejlev research station

Name of Institution: Aalborg University

Type of Institution: University

Level of Access: Transnational

Other partners: nan

Keywords: Sewer research, monitoring station

Thematic Area: Combined;Stormwater

Country: Denmark

City: Aalborg

Cost of Access:On request

Description:

The Frejlev research station was established in 1996 and is a sewer research and monitoring station. The facility receives combined and separated sewage water from the sub-urban city Frejlev. The city has around 2800 inhabitants and consists primarily of residential areas. Frejlev is located approximately 7 km west of Aalborg. The single most unique feature of this facility is that it provides access to a continuous flow of sewage water. Its location fairly upstream in the urban drainage system ensures a uniform and constant quality and composition of the sewage water, at a state where it is transported in the system. The facility is underground and offers large flexibility for any research activity that requires in-line access to raw sewage water, as the volume for experimental activity is approximately (10 m x 10 m x 3 m).The facility is equipped with sensor and data acquisition required for the most common sewer process measurements such as pH, dissolved oxygen, conductivity, sulphide gas (H₂S) and automated water samplers. Pumps, electromagnetic valves and PLC's are also available for controlling flow conditions. Finally, the research station is equipped with gas installations that currently are being used for the injection of hydrogen, H₂S and carbon dioxide (CO₂) into a setup for studying corroding sewer pipes.

Current Status: Active

Scale: Field (1:1)

Performance of
urban assets

Assets
deterioration

Digital water
solutions

R&D platform dedicated to treatment wetland for treating urban water - REFLET

INRAE

Name of Institution: INRAE

Country: France

Type of Institution: Research centre;

City: Lyon

Level of Access: Transnational

Cost of Access: On request

Other partners: nan

Keywords: Treatment wetlands, combine sewer, CSO, wastewater

Thematic Area: Wastewater; Combined; Stormwater;

Description:

The Lyon-based REFLET R&D platform provides access for consultants, contractors and project owners to a set of custom tools for developing and validating green systems for treating wastewater, sludge and urban discharges during rainfall events (actual effluents). Overseen by a specialist research team competent across various study scales (laboratory, pilot set-ups, semi-industrial prototypes, up to full-scale), this platform makes it possible to conduct original and innovative work, enhancing the understanding of processes in pursuit of operational objectives.

Current Status: Active

Scale: Pilot

SuDS
solutions

<https://eng-reversaal.lyon-grenoble.hub.inrae.fr/equipment-platforms/reflet>

Green ROOf experimental Facility

Name of Institution: Institut National des Sciences Appliquées de Lyon

Country: France

Type of Institution: University;

City: Lyon

Level of Access: Transnational

Cost of Access: On request

Other partners: nan

Keywords: green roof, hydrological performance, long term monitoring, evapotranspiration

Thematic Area: Stormwater;

Description:

GROOF is a set of six structures designed to receive various types of green roofs for long term experiments (some months to several years) aiming to monitor the behavior of green roofs (interception, storage, evaporation and evapotranspiration, state of vegetation, etc.), to estimate their hydrological performance and to provide data for modelling purposes. It is installed on the top of a building at INSA Lyon. Each structure is a 3m * 3m square which can receive a green roof for experiments. It lies on 4 feet which include strain gauges allowing measuring continuously the total weight of the facility and thus deriving evapotranspiration which remains one of the most difficult parameter to measure in green roofs. The other sensors are a complete weather station (rainfall, air humidity, temperature, pressure, wind speed and direction, solar radiation, etc.), flowmeters, soil moisture, and a hyperspectral camera to monitor the state of the vegetation.

Current Status: Active

Scale: Pilot

SuDS solutions

inpreparation

Django Reinhardt detention and settling Basin (DRB)

Name of Institution: Institut National des Sciences Appliquées Lyon

Country: France

Type of Institution: University;

City: Lyon

Level of Access: Transnational

Cost of Access: On request

Other partners: OTHU partners

Keywords: Stormwater, sediment, pollution, monitoring

Thematic Area: Stormwater;

Description:

The DRB is monitored under the framework of the field observatory for urban water management (<http://www.graie.org/othu/>) or OTHU in French (standing for Observatoire de Terrain en Hydrologie Urbaine). OTHU is an observation-based partnership launched in Lyon (France) in 1999 and supported by the Greater Lyon Metropolis, the Rhone Mediterranean Corsica Water Agency (RMC water agency), the national department of research and innovation, and 10 organisations including 9 academic partners and 1 association mainly in charge of the design and dissemination of research outcomes. OTHU aims to improve knowledge and develop new technology in the field of Urban Water Management. It promotes the cooperation among researchers from different scientific fields, as well as the collaboration between researchers and end-users. One of the OTHU sites is the DRB located in Chassieu (in the east part of the metropolis of Lyon). This DRB represents the outlet of an industrial watershed of 185 ha, with an impervious rate of 75%. This detention basin has a base surface of 11000m² and is composed of two inlets (inlet 1 conveying the majority of in-flows), an outlet, a gutter guiding the flow to three orifices during dry periods, and an overflow when the water height exceeds the retention wall. It is an open basin designed to be empty between two rainfall events.

Current Status: Active

Scale: Field (1:1)

Runoff
pollution

Urban
flooding

Performance of
urban assets

OTHU SUDS including a swale, a trench and a porous car park

Name of Institution: Institut national des sciences appliquées de Lyon

Country: France

Type of Institution: University;

City: Villeurbanne

Level of Access: Transnational

Cost of Access: On request

Other partners: nan

Keywords: stormwater, swale, trench, porous pavement, reservoir structure

Thematic Area: Stormwater;

Description:

The three SUDS are part of the field observatory for urban water management (OTHU), and have been designed and monitored in the framework of the Micromegas project granted by the RMC water agency and the french agency for biodiversity. If micropollutants (MP) removal measurements for centralized system (e.g. retention basin) are commonly investigated, little is known about long term field measurements of in-situ SUDS such as swales or trenches. Flow gauges installation and discharge measurements, as well as MP load assessment are quite challenging tasks for SUDS which may deliver very small flows. In addition, sampling procedure without disturbing the operation of SUDS is also hard to achieve, particularly to get representative variability according to the rainfall dynamic. Hence, monitoring activity of SUDS has to be performed in a proper way to collect reliable data on flow rates and MP concentrations. Flow rates and MP removal assessment have been recorded during 4 years. Water quality (MP concentrations, temperature, and conductivity) and quantity (rainfall intensity and inlet and outlet flow rates) will be monitored in the framework of OTHU research programme and data will be shared with CO-Udlabs consortium. The MP selected are the ones which have already been detected or quantified in previous studies (i.e metals (14), PAHs (16), pesticides (9), alkylphenols (8), PBDEs (7)) or/and that are known to be harmful to the environment. Most of them are listed as priority substances in the European Water Framework Directive. The analyses are also conducted on dissolved and particulate phases in order to evaluate their ability to reach underground or surface water environments.

Current Status: Active

Scale: Field (1:1)

SuDS solutions

Urban flooding

Runoff pollution

Performance of urban assets

Large Test Facility (IKT LTF)

Name of Institution: IKT - Institute for Underground Infrastructure

Country: Germany

Type of Institution: Research centre; Small-Medium Enterprise (SME);

City: Gelsenkirchen

Level of Access: Transnational

Cost of Access: On request

Other partners: nan

Keywords: deterioration urban drainage assets, pipe-soil-system, load-bearing, infiltration, exfiltration

Thematic Area: Wastewater; Stormwater; Combined;

Description:

IKT LTF ist a flexible facility is 18 m x 6 m x 6 m and offers the possibility of simulating on site conditions and at 1:1 scale under realistic soil, groundwater and traffic load conditions. Flow rates and traffic loads can be regulated up to 50 L/s and 1000 kN at frequencies up to 5 Hz respectively.

Current Status: Active

Scale: Field (1:1)

In-sewer process

Performance of urban assets

SuDS solutions

Assets deterioration

Hydraulic Test Stand (IKT TEST)

Name of Institution: IKT - Institute for Underground Infrastructure

Country: Germany

Type of Institution: Research centre; Small-Medium Enterprise (SME);

City: Gelsenkirchen

Level of Access: Transnational

Cost of Access: On request

Other partners: nan

Keywords: stormwater treatment, rainwater infiltration, hydraulic performance

Thematic Area: Stormwater;

Description:

The IKT's hydraulic test stand is a modular construction with a water transport and circulation system (max. flow rate 50 l/s), which can be adapted to the scientific question.

Current Status: Active

Scale: Laboratory

Runoff pollution

Performance of urban assets

SuDS solutions

Lab for sustainable pipe and drainage materials (IKT SDM)

Name of Institution: IKT - Institute for Underground Infrastructure

Country: Germany

Type of Institution: Research centre; Small-Medium Enterprise (SME);

City: Gelsenkirchen

Level of Access: Transnational

Cost of Access: On request

Other partners: nan

Keywords: mechanical/thermal loading of urban drainage assets

Thematic Area: Wastewater; Stormwater; Combined;

Description:

IKT's SDM LAB exists of different component to simulate different impacts and influences für pipe and drainage materials (e.g. UV weathering, freeze-thaw cycles, climatic impacts simultaneously with traffic load, creep strength), bursting test, vibration testing, steel ball drops tests.

Current Status: Active

Scale: Field (1:1)

In-sewer process

Performance of urban assets

IKT Heavy Rain Test Facility (IKT RTF)

Name of Institution: IKT - Institute for Underground Infrastructure

Country: Germany

Type of Institution: Research centre; Small-Medium Enterprise (SME);

City: Gelsenkirchen

Level of Access: Transnational

Cost of Access: On request

Other partners: nan

Keywords:

Thematic Area: Stormwater;

Description:

In IKT's Heavy Rain Testing Facility rainwater flows of roads, residential and commercial areas on a scale of 1:1 a can be simulated. This facility consists of a flexible field measuring 20 m x 10 m. Rain and high water flows can be simulated to test e.g. kerbstones, gutters, gullies, manholes and pipes as well as state-of-the-art rainwater retention equipment.

Current Status: Under development

Scale: Field (1:1)

Urban flooding

Runoff pollution

Performance of urban assets

SuDS solutions

Urban Observatory

Name of Institution: Institute of Urban and Industrial Water Management

Type of Institution: University;

Level of Access: Transnational

Other partners: Stadtentwässerung Dresden, Stadt Dresden

Keywords: urban streams, interaction sewer streams, online monitoring

Thematic Area: Wastewater;Stormwater;Combined;

Country: Germany

City: Dresden

Cost of Access:Free

Description:

The Urban Observatory consists of eight measurement stations in the catchment of Lockwitzbach and Geberbach, both are small streams flowing through the city of Dresden. In the Lockwitzbach catchment there are two stations directly located in the creek and three more in the sewer network (one in a storm water outlet & two in combined sewers) discharging in the creek during (heavy) rain events.

Current Status: Active

Scale: Field (1:1)

Runoff pollution

In-sewer process

SuDS solutions

Digital water solutions

1:1 Rain Garden

Name of Institution: Università della Calabria
Type of Institution: University;Administration;
Level of Access: Transnational
Other partners: nan

Country: Italy
City: Cerisano (CS)
Cost of Access:Free

Keywords:
Thematic Area: Stormwater;

Description:
 The Rain Garden is under development and it will be installed in the city of Cerisano

Current Status: Under development

Scale: Field (1:1)

Urban flooding

Runoff pollution

Performance of urban assets

SuDS solutions

Urban Drainage Network

Name of Institution: Università della Calabria
Type of Institution: University;Administration;
Level of Access: Transnational
Other partners: nan

Country: Italy
City: Cerisano (CS)
Cost of Access:Free

Keywords:
Thematic Area: Stormwater;

Description:

A part of the urban drainage network of Cerisano city will be monitored by devices and sensors to check water level/flow and quality of the water (turbidity, etc.)

Current Status: Under development

Scale: Pilot

Urban flooding

Runoff pollution

In-sewer process

Performance of urban assets

1:1 permeable pavement

Name of Institution: Università della Calabria

Type of Institution: University;

Level of Access: Transnational

Other partners: nan

Keywords:

Thematic Area: Stormwater;

Country: Italy

City: Rende

Cost of Access:Free

Description:

The permeable pavement has an area of 154 m², an average slope of 2%, and a total profile depth of 0.98 m. It consists of 5 layers. Inflow and Outflow from the pavement are measured in time.

Current Status: Active

Scale: Field (1:1)

Urban flooding

Runoff pollution

Performance of urban assets

SuDS solutions

1:1 Green roof demonstration site

Name of Institution: Università della Calabria

Type of Institution: University;

Level of Access: Transnational

Other partners: nan

Country: Italy

City: Rende

Cost of Access:Free

Keywords:

Thematic Area: Stormwater;

Description:

The GR demonstration site consists of 4 sectors of around 50 m² each. Three sectors are vegetated while the last one is a conventional roof (flat) used for comparison. Inflow, Outflow, and climatic variables (hydrothermal, temperature, etc) are measured in time.

Current Status: Active

Scale: Field (1:1)

Urban flooding

Runoff pollution

Performance of urban assets

SuDS solutions

1:1 Agricultural roof demonstration site

Name of Institution: Università della Calabria

Type of Institution: University;

Level of Access: Transnational

Other partners: nan

Country: Italy

City: Rende

Cost of Access: Free

Keywords:

Thematic Area: Stormwater;

Description:

A 150 m² agricultural roof with an innovative drainage layer. Inflow, Outflow, and climatic variables (hydrothermal, temperature, etc) are measured in time.

Current Status: Active

Scale: Field (1:1)

Urban flooding

Runoff pollution

Performance of urban assets

SuDS solutions

<https://www.topfree.info/>

1:1 Green Roof Demonstration site 2

Name of Institution: Università della Calabria

Type of Institution: University;

Level of Access: Transnational

Other partners: nan

Country: Italy

City: Rende

Cost of Access:Free

Keywords:

Thematic Area: Stormwater;

Description:

A 150 m² novel multipurpose self-irrigated green roof. Inflow, Outflow, and climatic (hydrothermal, temperature, etc) are measured in time. It is quite new so the acquisition data system is still in progress

Current Status: Active

Scale: Field (1:1)

Urban flooding

Runoff pollution

Performance of urban assets

SuDS solutions

1:1 Green Wall system

Name of Institution: Università della Calabria

Type of Institution: University;

Level of Access: Transnational

Other partners: nan

Country: Italy

City: Rende

Cost of Access:Free

Keywords:

Thematic Area: Stormwater;

Description:

An innovative modular green wall system (hereafter referred to as GW) was implemented on the façade of a residential building to manage urban stormwater. This green wall, consisting of a system of panels, collects rainwater from the roof surface. Each GW panel has a dimension of 100 cm × 100 cm with two boxes for the growth of plants. Each box has a height of 16 cm, a length of 100 cm and a width of 14.5 cm and has the same stratigraphy consisting of a surface layer covered with plants; a deep soil substrate (70% Irish peat and 30% perlite); a filter layer; a drainage layer of clay pebbles.

Current Status: Active

Scale: Field (1:1)

Urban flooding

Runoff pollution

Performance of urban assets

SuDS solutions

Real-scale Blue Roof installations

Name of Institution: University of Catania

Type of Institution: University

Level of Access: Transnational

Other partners: nan

Country: Italy

City: Catania (Sicily)

Cost of Access: On request

Keywords: Urban runoff control, flow attenuation; rooftop installations

Thematic Area: Stormwater; Combined

Description:

We have three different types of 1:1 blue roof pilots mounted on a large flat terrace of one of the buildings of the University Campus. The three pilots are one modular tray-based blue roof (the older one), and two (more recent) additional blue roofs made in mats of artificial turfs and stones. The three pilots are continuously monitored collecting precipitation, runoff, flow discharge, and other climatic parameters. Data are available starting from late 2018 up to today. Results of the long-term performances of the three pilots are available in the recent scientific literature.

Current Status: Active

Scale: Field (1:1)

Runoff City

Norwegian
University of
Life Sciences

Name of Institution: Norwegian University of Life Sciences

Type of Institution: University;

Level of Access: Transnational

Other partners: nan

Country: Norway

City: Ås / Oslo

Cost of Access:Free

Keywords: Rainfall simulator, nature based solutions, basement flooding, competition

Thematic Area: Stormwater;Combined;

Description:

The research infrastructure consists of a 3D-printed urban model at a 1:100 scale, covering a total area of 2 m². The model represents a small cityscape including roads, paved surfaces, buildings, and a functional drainage system with gutters, drains and pipes. A rainfall simulator positioned above the model allows for user-controlled precipitation events with intensities up to 330 mm/h. During high-intensity, short-duration rainfall events, the capacity of the combined sewer system is exceeded, resulting in basement flooding in one of the buildings. Real-time monitoring is conducted for precipitation, discharge through the sewer network, and water levels associated with basement flooding. To investigate the effectiveness of nature-based solutions, elements such as bioretention cells, intensive and extensive green roofs, permeable pavements, and vegetated areas are introduced into the model using sponge materials to simulate hydrologic effects. These interventions reduce and delay runoff, significantly mitigating the extent of basement flooding. The infrastructure is utilized for both educational purposes and research, including studies on machine learning applications, hydraulic model development, and multi-objective optimization techniques (cost-benefit analysis).

Current Status: Active

Scale: Laboratory

Urban
flooding

Performance of
urban assets

SuDS
solutions

An international webpage is currently under development

Green Roof Test Facility of the Norwegian Landscape Laboratory

Norwegian
University of
Life Sciences

Name of Institution: Norwegian University of Life Sciences

Country: Norway

Type of Institution: University

City: Ås

Level of Access: Remote

Cost of Access: Free

Other partners: NVE, Bergknapp, Leca (Saint-Gobain)

Keywords: green roof, detention, smart drain

Thematic Area: Stormwater

Description:

The facility was established in spring 2018 to study the effect of the roofs as a storm water management option, and measurements have been collected since summer/autumn 2018. The facility consists of three 50 m² test roofs, of which one roof is an ordinary black reference roof and two roofs are identical green roofs with a 150 mm thick storage layer of finely crushed LECA (0 – 6 mm) under a 40 mm thick sedum mat. The roofs are instrumented for measuring hydrologically relevant variables and the collected data is available for free through NVE's portal Sildre: "https://sildre.nve.no/station/5.10.0?5.10.0tab=1" Currently, one green roof is being converted into a facility with a remotely controlled drain, while the other green roof is retained as a reference and to form long time series with the same roof structure.

Current Status: Active

Scale: Pilot

Urban
flooding

SuDS
solutions

Digital water
solutions

<https://www.nmbu.no/fakulteter/fakultet-landskap-og-samfunn/forsker-pa-gronne-tak-i-norges-landskapslaboratorium-nmbu>

Risvollan

Name of Institution: Norwegian University of Science and Technology

Country: Norway

Type of Institution: University;

City: Trondheim

Level of Access: National

Cost of Access: On request

Other partners: Trondheim Municipality, Norwegian Water Resources and Energy Directorate

Keywords: Urban hydrology

Thematic Area: Stormwater; Wastewater;

Description:

Risvollan measurement station has been active since 1986, and measures urban-hydrological parameters from a residential area in Trondheim, with catchment size 0.22 km². Foul and stormwater discharges are measured, as well as temperature, precipitation and snow-storage/melting. The ownership of the station is shared between NTNU, Trondheim municipality and the Norwegian Water Resources and Energy Directorate (NVE)

Current Status: Active

Scale: Field (1:1)

Urban flooding

Runoff pollution

Performance of urban assets

Digital water solutions

<https://sildre.nve.no/station/123.38.0?123.38.0tab=2>

Real Scale Dual Drainage with 2 gullies and 2 manholes

UNIVERSIDADE D COIMBRA

Name of Institution: University of Coimbra

Type of Institution: University;

Level of Access: Transnational

Other partners: nan

Keywords: dual drainage, gully, manhole, surcharge

Thematic Area: Stormwater;

Country: Portugal

City: Coimbra

Cost of Access: On request

Description:

A real-scale dual drainage system comprising 10 m long and 0.5 wide flume with two gullies at the bottom connected with two 1 m diameter drop manholes linked by a 0.3 m pipe allowing both surface and sewer drainage. Equipment such as several electric valves, 16 pressure transducers and flow-meters.

Current Status: Active

Scale: Field (1:1)

In-sewer
process

Digital water
solutions

1:1 Street Model Rainfall Simulator (STREET)

UNIVERSIDADE DA CORUÑA

Name of Institution: Universidade da Coruña
Type of Institution: University; Research centre;
Level of Access: Transnational
Other partners: nan

Country: Spain
City: A Coruña
Cost of Access: Paid

Keywords: Rainfall, street flooding, pollutants mobilization
Thematic Area: Stormwater;

Description:

The STREET model is a full-scale urban drainage facility of 36 m² for studying rainfall processes, street flooding and pollutants mobilization on the street surface and through pipes.

Realistic rainfall in terms of uniformity and rain energy can be generated with 30, 50 and 80 mm/h intensity by a dripper system. A porous pavement with a transverse slope of 2% and a longitudinal slope of 0.5% is currently installed on street roadway, but it can be changed to other surfaces typologies.

An upstream surface runoff generator and a drainage system consisting of 85- and 190-mm diameter pipes complete the facility. All the system and the model surface are instrumented with depth sensors to record flow and pipe depths, UDV profilers for pipe velocity measurements and flowmeters.

A large-scale PIV system has been optimized to characterize 2D velocity maps. Finally, continuous turbidity probes and grab samplers are available to determine TSS and other pollutants processes.

Current Status: Active

Scale: Field (1:1)

Urban flooding

Runoff pollution

Performance of urban assets

SuDS solutions

Digital water solutions

<https://co-udlabs.eu/access/research-facilities/11-street-model/>

Rainfall Simulator Scientific Platform for Urban Runoff Tests (BLOCK)

Name of Institution: Universidade da Coruña
Type of Institution: University; Research centre;
Level of Access: Transnational
Other partners: nan

Country: Spain
City: A Coruña
Cost of Access: Paid

Keywords: Rainfall, urban runoff, roofs, drainage
Thematic Area: Stormwater;

Description:

The facility represents an urban intersection in a 100 m² scale model (1:4) for studying rainfall-runoff transformation and pollutants mobilization. This unique structure considers surface and drainage network flows and incorporates:

a realistic rainfall simulator with intensities of 30, 50 and 80 mm/h; roof surfaces formed by curved ceramic tiles with adjustable slopes; 2 T-shaped streets, with concrete pavement with a transverse slope of 2% and a longitudinal slope of 1%; 4 gully-pots and a channel for the collection of runoff downstream; 4 manholes; 2 surface runoff generators located upstream of the intersection; a drainage system consisting of transparent plastic pipes with diameters of 200 mm; 2 flow contribution systems to simulate the upstream pipe flow conditions of the model; and (ix) a LSPIV optimized system to monitor 2D flow surface velocity maps. In addition, numerous flow meters, and depth, pressure, suspended solids and conductivity sensors are available, as well as complete sample analysis, for monitoring hydraulic and sediment transport processes.

Current Status: Active

Scale: Field (1:1)

<https://co-udlabs.eu/access/research-facilities/block/>

Bens WWTP Flume Facility (BENS)

UNIVERSIDADE DA CORUÑA

Name of Institution: Universidade da Coruña
Type of Institution: University; Research centre;
Level of Access: Transnational
Other partners: EMALCSA, EDAR Bens

Country: Spain
City: A Coruña
Cost of Access: Paid

Keywords: water pollution, sediments, velocity
Thematic Area: Wastewater;

Description:

The flume consists of a 10 m length and 0.8 m width metallic bench for studying sewer processes using real wastewater from the pre-treatment system of A Coruña WWTP with a maximum flow discharge of 30 L/s.

Wastewater flow is split from the inlet tank through two v-notch weirs and falls into a discharge chamber before going through two different pipes. Wastewater is discharged in a downstream chamber where an automatic tailgate is placed to set downstream boundary conditions.

The slope can be changed from 0.5% to 6%. Wastewater loads can be monitored in the inlet and downstream tanks of the flume by using online turbidity and light absorbance probes. Several auto-samplers can be installed to determine conventional pollutant parameters. Water depth sensors are used for measuring the water depths along the pipes and in the inlet tank. The system also has an ultrasonic flowmeter, and punctual velocity measurements can be performed with Acoustic Doppler Velocimeter.

Furthermore, photogrammetric techniques and sampling analyses have been optimized to obtain the deposited sediment volume and composition respectively. Finally, an UDV UB-Lab profiler is available to determine velocity and acoustic turbidity profiles.

Current Status: Active

Scale: Field (1:1)

In-sewer process

SuDS solutions

Digital water solutions

<https://co-udlabs.eu/access/research-facilities/bens/>

Campus SUDS

UNIVERSIDADE DA CORUÑA

Name of Institution: Universidade da Coruña
Type of Institution: University; Research centre
Level of Access: Transnational
Other partners: nan

Country: Spain
City: A Coruña
Cost of Access: On request

Keywords: Green roofs, bioretention areas, constructed wetland, runoff sandtraps
Thematic Area: Wastewater; Stormwater; Combined

Description:

The campus has implemented several sustainable drainage systems (SUDS) to manage stormwater effectively: **Bioretention Area in the Engineering School Parking Lot:** This system collects surface water from the parking lot (approx. 1300 m²) and directs it to a bioretention area. The water infiltrates through a topsoil layer into modular storage boxes. **Sedimentation-Filtration Tank in the Computer Science Faculty Parking Lot:** Surface water from the parking lot (approx. 1300 m²) is directed to an underground sedimentation chamber. From there, it passes through a sand filtration system with two treatment lines to analyze different filtering and adsorbing media. The filtered water is collected via perforated drainage pipes. **Experimental Green Roof Models at the Engineering School:** This project includes three types of green roofs, each covering about 36 m²: (i) sloped vegetated roof, (ii) flat vegetated roof, and (iii) flat gravel roof. Each roof has a control chamber for analyzing outflows and a general chamber connected to the campus stormwater network. **Retention Pond and Wetland for the Sports Pavilion Roof:** This system features a retention pond with a permanent volume of 12 m³, allowing for water storage during rain events. The pond is connected to a horizontal flow wetland with helophyte vegetation. The outflow connects to the drainage system. **Water Flow Monitoring Installation for the Campus:** To evaluate the impact of progressively implementing SUDS techniques, a control section has been set up at the campus hydrological closure. This allows monitoring of the combined sewer network, stormwater drainage network, and the Lagar River, the natural flow of the basin.

Current Status: Active

Scale: Field (1:1)

Pilot roofs

Name of Institution: Luleå University of Technology

Type of Institution: University;

Level of Access: Transnational

Other partners: nan

Keywords: Roof runoff, pollution sources, metal, organic contaminants

Thematic Area: Stormwater;

Country: Sweden

City: Luleå

Cost of Access:Free

Description:

Ten different building surface materials are installed on pilot-scale panels at the Luleå University of Technology (LTU) campus. Each material is installed on three replicate panels, each measuring 1 × 2 m with a 10% slope. The materials include bitumen-based roofing felt, shingle, Corten steel, coated steel, zinc sheets, copper sheets, galvanized steel, two types of PVC membranes, and titanium-zinc sheets. Stainless steel panels are used as controls to distinguish pollutant contributions from atmospheric deposition. The panels were installed in a randomized order and exposed to weather conditions year-round. The City of Luleå, located in northern Sweden, has potential sources of airborne pollutants from a steel production plant and a district heating plant. The region experiences southerly or southwesterly winds and has a subarctic climate with typical precipitation pH around 5.

Current Status: Active

Scale: Pilot

Runoff
pollution

<https://www.ltu.se/en/research/research-subjects/urban-water-engineering/drizzle/research-on-stormwater-quality/stormwater-quality/2023-12-12-sources-and-characterization-of-stormwater-pollutants>

Pilot green roofs

Name of Institution: Luleå University of Technology

Type of Institution: University;

Level of Access: Transnational

Other partners: nan

Keywords: Green roof, hydrology

Thematic Area: Stormwater;

Country: Sweden

City: Luleå

Cost of Access:Free

Description:

The pilot green roofs consist of thirty green roof modules, 1 m wide and 2 m long, with a slope of 6.2 degrees, exposed to the south. The modules have 20-mm raised edges to prevent runoff spilling from the sides. There are 6 green roof treatments (Bare substrate, Sedum, Competitive, Stress tolerant, Ruderal and Mix) with 5 replicates of each. The green roof modules are built from wood and covered with bitumen tar water-proofing material and a thin geotextile, to prevent any loss of substrate through the perforated steel plate at the short end of the module draining runoff into a collecting gutter. The modules are filled with 100 mm of a commonly-used green roof substrate, with 1.13 g cm⁻³ measured bulk density and a water-holding capacity of 38 %. The substrate consists of crushed scoria, crushed gravel, sand, clay granulate, and peat with a 5 % organic content. It has a grain size composition of 3 % clay, 6 % fine and medium silt, 13 % coarse silt and fine sand, 49 % medium sand and coarse sand, and 29 % fine and medium gravel. The runoff drips into the covered gutter and can be collected through a hose into weighing buckets, to measure the flow continuously. Pilot roofs in bitumen tar and stainless steel are also available as a control.

Current Status: Inactive

Scale: Pilot

SuDS
solutions

<https://www.ltu.se/en/research/research-subjects/urban-water-engineering/research-projects/stormwater/research-on-stormwater/2023-12-11-improving-green-roof-performance-in-demanding-climates-2015-2019>

Brunen-Brunen

Name of Institution: Luleå University of Technology

Type of Institution: University;

Level of Access: Transnational

Other partners: nan

Keywords: Road runoff, continuous monitoring, pollution

Thematic Area: Stormwater;

Country: Sweden

City: Luleå

Cost of Access:Free

Description:

Surface runoff from a 660 road catchment (Södra Hamnleden) follows a curb along the roadside and is collected in a roadside drain leading to a manhole where a sampling point has been constructed. The road has a slope of 2.6% and an average daily traffic of 7400 vehicles/day. The manhole has been equipped with an inline detention volume (siphon-like structure) designed to hold approximately 10 liters of runoff in which water quality sensors can be installed, as well as a V-notch weir with a level sensor to measure flow, located in the same manhole downstream of the siphon well.

Current Status: Active

Scale: Field (1:1)

Runoff
pollution

Sundsvall biofilter

Name of Institution: Luleå University of Technology

Type of Institution: University;

Level of Access: Transnational

Other partners: nan

Country: Sweden

City: Sundsvall

Cost of Access:Free

Keywords: Green infrastructure, biofilter, stormwater treatment, road runoff

Thematic Area: Stormwater;

Description:

This field site consists of a gross pollutant trap (GPT)-biofilter/sand filter treatment train (TT) located in Sundsvall, Sweden. The system receives stormwater from an impervious catchment area of 4.7 ha including the 1.9 ha E4 highway bridge with an average traffic load of 13,000 vehicles/day, a highway exit way, main roads associated with a roundabout and sidewalk paths. The TT was designed according to German stormwater biofilter guidelines for treatment of highway runoff and was constructed in 2018 i.e. it was 3 years old at the time of sampling. Downstream of the road catchment, the collected stormwater is first transported by a 100-m-long underground pipe (slope 0.5 % and diameter 0.8 m) to the GPT section which includes a sedimentation chamber and an oil separator. The stormwater in the GPT is then discharged through a stepwise valve-controlled siphon system to three parallel filter cells divided by EPDM membranes where it infiltrates through the sand-based filter media. One of the filter cells is non-vegetated (sand filter SF), and the other two are vegetated (biofilters BFC and BF). The vegetation layer is made of salt-tolerant meadow sod with 17 different plant species pre-cultivated in a 3–4 cm deep sandy or silty-sandy soil with 2.5–5 % w/w mulch. The filter media in one of the biofilters (BFC) is amended with 10 % w/w crushed grey chalk (CaCO₃). Afterwards, the treated stormwater is drained from the cells through a gravel drain layer with embedded drainpipes, then led to three sampling wells, and finally collected and released to the downstream recipient. If the runoff inflow exceeds the GPT's active detention volume (23.3 m³) during each charging and discharge step, the stormwater is bypassed from the TT at the GPT entrance.

Current Status: Active

Scale: Field (1:1)

SuDS
solutions

Växjö biofilters

Name of Institution: Luleå University of Technology

Type of Institution: University;

Level of Access: Transnational

Other partners: nan

Keywords: Green infrastructure, biofilter, stormwater treatment

Thematic Area: Stormwater;

Country: Sweden

City: Växjö

Cost of Access:Free

Description:

The site consists of four vegetated biofilters built in 2019 in Växjö, Sweden, along a road with an average daily traffic of approximately 2500 vehicles. The facilities receive stormwater runoff from the road, pedestrian, and commercial/industrial areas. Each biofilter has one main along with smaller curb-opening inlets equipped with small presedimentation forebays. Two of the biofilters have a media comprised a mixture of 85 vol.% sand filter material and 15 vol.% clay-free soil (AMA Jord type B® with 5 wt.% mulch for plant growth). The other two biofilters (SB1 and SB2) have the same sand composition, which was amended with 10 vol.% (i.e., 2.1 wt%) biochar and 5 vol.% AMA soil.

Current Status: Active

Scale: Field (1:1)

SuDS
solutions

<https://www.ltu.se/en/research/research-subjects/urban-water-engineering/research-projects/stormwater/research-on-stormwater/2023-12-11-treatment-of-stormwater-in-bioretenion-effect-of-biochar-amendments-2021-2022>

Experimental Hall

eawag
aquatic research 000

Name of Institution: Swiss Federal Institute of Aquatic Science and Technology

Country: Switzerland

Type of Institution: Research centre;

City: Dübendorf

Level of Access: Transnational

Cost of Access: On request

Other partners: nan

Keywords: Pollution Monitoring, Sewer Processes, Pilot- Field- and Laboratory experiments, Wastewater treatment,

Thematic Area: Wastewater; Stormwater; Combined;

Description:

The experimental facility at Eawag is a key site for advancing wastewater research. It includes the Eawag wastewater treatment plant (WWTP), which treats real wastewater from the town of Dübendorf, as well as spaces for pilot plants, numerous small reactors, laboratories, and workshops. Operated by the Process Engineering department, the facility supports the development and optimization of wastewater treatment methods on a small scale. Research topics include the production of nitrous oxide—a major greenhouse gas—in treatment processes. Collaboration with practical partners is central to testing and improving new technologies. The facility also supports interdisciplinary projects and is used by other Eawag departments. It serves as a training ground for students and PhD candidates, offering hands-on experience in real-world conditions.

Pilot plants developed and tested at the site help to bring innovative treatment processes into existing municipal systems, enabling practical evaluation and implementation.

Current Status: Active

Scale: Pilot

Runoff
pollution

In-sewer
process

Digital water
solutions

<https://www.eawag.ch/en/about-us/working/researchenvironment/experimental-facility/>

Urban Water Observatory

eawag
aquatic research ooo

Name of Institution: swiss federal institute of aquatic science and technology

Country: Switzerland

Type of Institution: Research centre;

City: Dübendorf

Level of Access: Transnational

Cost of Access: On request

Other partners: nan

Keywords: Urban water monitoring, Sensor networks, Transdisciplinary research, Wastewater infrastructure

Thematic Area: Wastewater; Stormwater; Combined;

Description:

The Urban Water Observatory (UWO) is a long-term initiative by ETH and Eawag launched in 2016 in Fehraltorf. It functions as a coordinated research lab, test bed, sensor platform, and hands-on classroom, all focused on spatially-distributed monitoring of urban water cycle processes.

Key goals of the UWO are to:

- *Conduct transdisciplinary environmental research within and across urban water systems

- *Address key questions on the future of water infrastructure

- *Promote transparency and public awareness around the urban water cycle

The UWO uses a dense network of sensors—more than one per hectare—to monitor rainfall, flows, water levels, and other system states across the sewer network, rivers, and groundwater. Data is transmitted using modern wireless technologies like LoRaWAN.

By capturing high-resolution data, UWO supports research on how rainfall drives surface runoff, pipe flow, overflow activity, and affects surrounding systems like wastewater treatment plants, groundwater, and rivers. The monitoring network is now being expanded to include water quality indicators such as pH, conductivity, and turbidity.

Current Status: Active

Scale: Field (1:1)

Runoff pollution

In-sewer process

SuDS solutions

Digital water solutions

<https://www.eawag.ch/en/department/sww/projects/urban-water-observatory/>

Hydraulic laboratory and calibration plant

STEBATEC®

Name of Institution: STEBATEC AG

Country: Switzerland

Type of Institution: Small-Medium Enterprise (SME);

City: 2555 Brügg / Biel

Level of Access: Transnational

Cost of Access: On request

Other partners: nan

Keywords: 1600 l/s, open channel, 1:1 Pilot tests, Supervised trials

Thematic Area: Wastewater; Stormwater; Combined;

Description:

- Permanently stable flow rates freely adjustable in the range from 0.5 to 1600 l/s - Accumulation and pressure range: 0m to 10m - Test channel LxW: 20mx3m

Current Status: Active

Scale: Pilot

Urban flooding

In-sewer process

Performance of urban assets

SuDS solutions

Digital water solutions

ICAIR

Name of Institution: University of Sheffield
Type of Institution: University;Research centre;
Level of Access: Transnational
Other partners: nan

Country: United Kingdom
City: Sheffield
Cost of Access:

Keywords:

Thematic Area: Wastewater;Stormwater;Combined;

Description:

Test cell for urban water infrastructure assets (e.g. interconnected water pipes, sewer pipes/chambers, inlet structures) and natural artefacts such as impermeable and permeable catchment surfaces, soil layers and voids can be created. The test cell is 45m long by 5m deep by 6m wide. This full-scale environment can be subjected to a controlled regime of sub-surface, pipe and surface flows and physical and chemical loadings and then the performance of the representative part of the urban water infrastructure system will be monitored.

Current Status: Active

Scale: Pilot

Urban flooding

Runoff pollution

In-sewer process

Performance of urban assets

SuDS solutions

Assets deterioration

Digital water solutions

<https://icair.ac.uk/capabilities>

A/B Flume

Name of Institution: University of Sheffield
Type of Institution: University;Research centre;
Level of Access: Transnational
Other partners: nan

Country: United Kingdom
City: Sheffield
Cost of Access:

Keywords:

Thematic Area: Stormwater;Combined;

Description:

Surface/Sewer flows interaction facility, 8 m x 4 m surface linked to a 75 mm drainage pipe work by a 240 mm ‘manhole’. Instrumented with depth and flow meters with access to PIV/PTV and optical measurement systems.

Current Status: Active

Scale: Laboratory

Urban flooding

Runoff pollution

Performance of urban assets

Annular Flume

Name of Institution: University of Sheffield
Type of Institution: University;Research centre;
Level of Access: Transnational
Other partners: nan

Country: United Kingdom
City: Sheffield
Cost of Access:

Keywords:

Thematic Area: Wastewater;Stormwater;

Description:

Annular channel with rectangular cross-section 0.20 m wide and a maximum available height of 0.48 m, which is placed in a 2.20 m external and 1.80 m internal diameter platform. An image acquisition system, physical sampling and pH, dissolved oxygen, conductivity sensors are available.

The temperature controlled annular flume is operated with up to 300 L of wastewater to simulate microbial and biochemical processes that would be found within a sewer or drainage system

Current Status: Active

Scale: Laboratory

In-sewer
process

RTC test facility

Name of Institution: University of Sheffield
Type of Institution: University;Research centre;
Level of Access: Transnational
Other partners: nan

Country: United Kingdom
City: Sheffield
Cost of Access:

Keywords:

Thematic Area: Stormwater;Combined;

Description:

Real Time Control Test facility, 35 m of 200 mm pipe with 4, 1 m diameter manholes and model CSO. Featuring automated gate and depth sensors and variable flow input and downstream control.

Current Status: Active

Scale: Laboratory

Urban flooding

Performance of urban assets

Digital water solutions

<https://www.sheffield.ac.uk/mac/research/groups/water-engineering>

Villanova Center for Resilient Water Systems

Name of Institution: Villanova University

Country: United States

Type of Institution: University; Research centre;

City: Villanova Pennsylvania Philadelphia Area

Level of Access: We have research Fields sites on campus and in Philadelphia, and Supporting Laboratories

Cost of Access: On request

Other partners: nan

Keywords: Stormwater Systems, resilience,

Thematic Area: Stormwater;

Description:

We have over twenty years of field research supported by our laboratories for resilient stormwater systems. We have and are currently monitoring several green infrastructure practices on campus, and off a highway in Philadelphia. A theme of research is linking monitored data to research on the processes of stormwater. Our Team includes Geotech, Water, and Environmental engineers, with support of Env. Scientists as well. Our brand new Laboratory building has added to merging field and laboratory research including sediment flumes, a dedicated water quality and geotechnical labs as well. Note Center faculty are also working with robotics for maintenance and inspection, and use of AI.

Current Status: Active

Scale: Field (1:1)

Urban flooding

Runoff pollution

SuDS solutions

Digital water solutions